

D1.1 Activity catalogue

for education, knowledge gain
and policy loop

Consortium:

 www.engage4bio.eu

 info@engage4bio.eu

@Engage4BIO

D1.1

Activity catalogue for education,
knowledge gain and policy loop

DELIVERABLE TYPE

WORK PACKAGE

LEADER

MONTH AND DATE OF DELIVERABLE

DISSEMINATION LEVEL

AUTHORS

03/31/2023

Public

Moholy-Nagy University of Art and Design

Rita Szerencsés

Programme

HORIZON
EUROPE

Start

Oct.2022

Grant Agreement

101059565

Duration

36 Months

CONTRIBUTORS

NAME	ORGANISATION
Maria Schrammel, Judith Feichtinger	Center for Social Innovation
Remco Kranendonk	Wageningen University & Research
Katalin Kálai	Bay Zoltán Nonprofit Ltd for Applied Research
Rita Szerencsés, Orsolya Polyacskó	Moholy-Nagy University of Art and Design
Kaisa Simola	CLIC Innovation Oy
Mona Roman, Hye Jung-Majanen	Metropolia University of Applied Sciences
Concetta Maria Messina	University of Palermo
Jeroen van den Eijnde	ArtEZ University of the Arts
Isabella Mantello, Kathrin Preinfalk	Business Upper Austria
Viola Pinzi	European Association for the Education of Adults (EAEA)

PEER REVIEWS

NAME	ORGANISATION
Kaisa Simola, Tiina Laiho	CLIC
Nóra Hatvani	BZN
Concetta Maria Messina	UNIPA
Remco Kranendonk	WR
Serena Fabbrini	APRE

REVISION HISTORY

VERSION	ORGANISATION	REVIEWER	MODIFICATIONS
V1	22/03/2023	Nóra Hatvani	Modifications in format and terminology
V1	24/03/2023	Concetta Maria Messina	Modification in terminology
V1	30/03/2023	Serena Fabbrini	Template format modification

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PARTNERS SHORT NAMES

ZSI	Zentrum für Soziale Innovation
WR	Wageningen University & Research
APRE	Agenzia per la Promozione della Ricerca Europea
BZN	Bay Zoltán Alkalmazott Kutatási Közhasznú Nonprofit Kft.
EAEA	European Association for the Education of Adults
MOME	Moholy-Nagy Művészeti Egyetem
ArteZ	Stichting Artez
CLIC	Clic Innovation Oy
TMG	Business Upper Austria – Oo Irtschaftsagentur Gmbh
MET	Metropolia Ammattikorkeakoulu Oy
UNIPA	Universita Degli Studi Di Palermo

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The Activity Catalogue aims to capture the most interesting activities related to training, knowledge gain and policy loops already existing in the Engage4BIO partnership. Curated in WP1 of the Engage4BIO project, the catalogue serves both the purpose of knowledge sharing, as well as a basis for WP2, where these activities will be adapted and tailored to regional specificities with the integration of art and design dimensions, and for WP3 which will provide the framework for implementing these activities. In addition, this is the first attempt at a short know-how sharing and “how we are doing a specific activity.” including tips for the partnership on “how others might implement something similar”.

Activities in this collection include outreach activities targeting the public and wide audiences or specific target groups; training and education, including co-creation methods; as well as activities for creating policy loop - all serving the purpose of knowledge gain.

This rich collection of innovative practices covers a great variety of formats, approaches, methods and scale. They range from a more informal brown bag lunch involving policymakers in a dialogue to a tightly structured hackathon event aiming to create innovative solutions to issues related to circular bioeconomy or related topics. Some use cutting-edge technology like robotics, others rely on the simplest tools like pen and paper. There is diversity with regard to the target groups as well, with a summer university addressing graduate and post-graduate students and others bringing together stakeholders from different walks of life. Some of the examples describe concrete activities and events in great detail, which have taken place before; while others describe formats rather, which can be adapted to different contexts and goals. In every case, it is a good idea to reach out to the partner hosting the activity for more details and practical tips.

Although the approaches may differ, hopefully each example will contain aspects that may inspire partners or give an idea, a practical tip for planning and implementing activities, as the catalogue seeks to serve the purposes of transferability and adaptation of internal good practices.

In this catalogue, Section 1 includes the template that the activity descriptions follow and Section 2 details the activities of the consortium partners.

ACTIVITY CATALOGUE STRUCTURE AND GUIDING QUESTIONS

ACTIVITY HOST / ORGANISER

Which institution is responsible for the activity? EAEA, CLIC, MOME, APRE, Wageningen, ZSI, Bay, ArtEZ, Metropolia, Unipa, Business Upper Austria

1 TYPE OF THE ACTIVITY

What type of activity is it? Training, event, communicational, educational, seminar, camp, expo, workshop, policy loop creation etc.)

2 FORMAT

How could the activity be described? Interactive or plenary? Online, offline, hybrid?

3 THEME / CHALLENGES

What is the core theme of the activity or the challenge the activity is trying to act upon?

4 AIM OF THE ACTIVITY

What is the activity trying to reach / solve / react upon?

5 SHORT DESCRIPTION

Max. 800-character general summary of the chosen activity - You can copy a paragraph from your website, from a press release, social media post / event, programme brochure etc.)

6 ORGANIZER TEAM

What is the composition and number of required organizer team members (e.g facilitators / moderators/technical support) For how long are they engaged, how many hours? Project based or permanent staff? etc.

7 TARGET GROUP

Who is addressed by the activity (direct or indirect target, such as audience, participants, etc.)

8 CRITICAL NUMBER OF PARTICIPANTS

What is the minimum and maximum number of participants involved in the activity?

9 DURATION

What is the duration of the activity? (How many minutes, hours, days, weeks, etc.?)

10 PREPARATION PERIOD

How much time is needed to prepare the activity? (How many days, weeks, months etc.?)

11 LOCATION

Where does the activity take place? Urban vs rural? Both? Public place vs classroom? Etc.

12 BUDGET AND SOURCES OF FINANCING

Approx. budget size? Coming from grants, investors? For-profit activity or non-profit?

13 SETTING AND MATERIALS NEEDED

Are there any special physical materials, equipment, settings needed to realize the activity? (Like 3D printer, AI glasses, street occupation permission, boat)

14 INFORMED CONSENT AND COPYRIGHT ISSUES (IF APPLICABLE)

Think about copyright, data collection, etc. Provide insight on your practice

15 OUTPUTS (IF APPLICABLE)

Are there any tangible outputs of the activity? -(Catalogue, magazine, case study, video, prototype, toolbox etc.) - Please describe!

16 IMPACT

What are the tangible / intangible impacts (long-term), short and midterm outcomes of the activity?

17 TOOLS

What tools or toolboxes are used to realize or during the activity, if any? Tools in a sense of methodical tools, intangible, non-physical tools, even software, digital programmes etc. Any tools used to plan / organize the activity? Map and gap canvas, BMC, ToC, Trello, etc.

18 COMMUNICATION

What kind of communication activities do you carry out before and after the activity? Channels? Style? Messages? Social Media? Creative communications tools used / applied? Is there any specific communication strategy applied? What is it? What type of communication materials are created (rollup, flyer, video, gif)?

EVALUATION AND REFLECTION

19 METHOD

Are there any methods or methodology applied to undertake the activity? Does the activity have its own method(ology)? Preliminary training is necessary to conduct the activity? Methods can be for example design thinking, agile method, artistic research, action-research, structured interview, any named co-creation method etc.. Please give a shorter insight, content can be elaborated more during the next work package. If applicable give information on the length of a session, group size etc.

20 STEP-BY-STEP INSTRUCTIONS

This is an operational category not methodology related. Sum-up the steps of realizing / undertaking the activity keeping in mind the understandability for external readers. What are the timely action items the organizers must execute in order to have the activity implemented? Different results are not a problem since editing will be the next step. Please read the example!

21 LINKS

Copy here the link where more information is available about the activity, like photos, videos, agenda, etc. You can also copy a website link of an article about the activity, or a link to an interview conducted with an organizer, or any further links to further reading, reports, case study documents, etc..

22 LESSONS LEARNED

What are the main takeaways related to the activity on different levels? Operational take-aways related to location, lengths of preparatory period or group dynamics, team set-up, materials supply etc.

23 KNOWLEDGE GAIN

What is the knowledge that is realized and gained among participants / target group and organizers? This is a more theoretical category. Like knowledge gain would be for example a decision maker as a participant heard for the first time about the creative solution in creating artificial corals to avoid flooding during a panel discussion. Or the initiator of the activity gained knowledge about the children invited to take part in the interactive activity, that it takes time to encourage them to participate so ice breaker games have to be inserted for next events)

24 PITFALLS / OBSTACLES

Did you encounter any barriers during the implementation process? Any risks worth considering?

25 VARIATIONS (IF APPLICABLE)

Is there any variation of the activity? Shorter - longer version, online or offline variances? Adaption to another field or by another organization?

26 TIPS FOR FUTURE IMPLEMENTERS / GOOD-TO-KNOWS

What are the aspects a future implementer should keep in-mind, be considerate about, pay extra attention to?

27 RECOMMENDATION

This activity is for you, future implementer, if...

Activity catalogue

EMBASSY OF SUSTAINABLE DESIGN AT THE DUTCH DESIGN WEEK EXHIBITION

ACTIVITY HOST / ORGANISER

Wageningen University and Research (WUR), The Netherlands

1 TYPE OF THE ACTIVITY

Exhibition

2 FORMAT

Dutch Design Week (DDW) is an offline event, the large design event in the Netherlands. The exhibition is open for the public for 9 days, from 1100-1800. Also, there was a business program from 10am to 11am and from 18h to 19h. Wageningen Research hosted a Bioeconomy stand with 2 persons every day, to explain and discuss the perspectives of bioeconomy to the visitors.

3 THEME / CHALLENGES

The overarching theme was bioeconomy. A stand with 3 value chains of bio-based products was prepared, from crop to intermediate building blocks to new applications.

4 AIM OF THE ACTIVITY

The aim was to connect with the general public, to inform them about the perspectives of bioeconomy by showing them 3 value chains of bio-based products and by explaining and discussing bioeconomy.

5 SHORT DESCRIPTION

The DDW is a public event which attracts professionals, as well as the general public. It was part of a larger exhibition, the Embassy of Sustainable Design, designed by curators, where all materials used were circular. The Embassy attracted 25000 visitors. Wageningen Research was in contact with many professionals, visiting the stand individually and in groups as well. In order to inform the visitors about the potential the bio-based economy, the value chain from plant to bio-based products was exhibited. Two crops were chosen and showed the intermediate and final products:

- ▶ Maize/Corn → PLA → packaging material, Biofoam, bioplastics (Mouse), textiles (T-shirt, bag)
- ▶ Miscanthus → Granulate (fibres/starch) → bioplastics (Lunchbox)
- ▶ Miscanthus → fibres → construction materials (concrete) or papers and packaging

The storyline was actively explained to the visitors and people were able to touch the products and ask questions. Also, the related processes were demonstrated in a video and a Prezi presentation. The video was about the construction of a wooden T-Shirt. A laptop was installed to test the knowledge of the visitors in a quiz and different folders and booklets with more detailed information were also available for interested visitors. There was constant interaction with the visitors.

6 ORGANIZER TEAM

The organizer team included researchers of bioeconomy, open for discussion with visitors, some communication specialists, as well as one of the Directors at the opening of the DDW. Wageningen participated with a large team of researchers who were open to discussions.

Wageningen Research took part in the Embassy of Sustainable Design which was an integrated exhibition, developed by the Embassy partners and two curators. The other Embassy partners were multinational companies such as IKEA, Friesland Campina and Renewi, all showing their ambitions related to circular economy. Further knowledge partners included the Universities of Delft and Eindhoven, the Design Academy, Artez Arnhem, representing designers who work with biomass and with waste materials.

To develop the exhibition, a team of 3 researchers and a communication expert worked together, and for hosting the stand 10 colleagues were mobilised.

7 TARGET GROUP

The main target group was the public, although professionals from companies and local governments were also interested, just like international delegations.

8 CRITICAL NUMBER OF PARTICIPANTS

For an exhibition format there is no critical number, although discussions can be held with a limited number of visitors at the same time.

9 DURATION

The Dutch Design Week lasted 9 days from the 10h-18h daily.

10 PREPARATION PERIOD

Preparing the stand required 1 day a week over 3 months, which totalled 15 days.

11 LOCATION

The stand was in the DDW venue, Brainport Eindhoven. The exhibition was organised in the at the Van Berlo Design Studio – the Innovation Powerhouse.

12 BUDGET AND SOURCES OF FINANCING

The total budget was 20.000-25.000 EUR, including the materials costs (approximately 5000-10.000 EUR) and the contributors' fees (15.000EUR).

13 SETTING AND MATERIALS NEEDED

In addition to the bio-based crops and the materials, a video, a screen and a laptop were used.

14 INFORMED CONSENT AND COPYRIGHT ISSUES (IF APPLICABLE)

-

15
OUTPUTS
(IF APPLICABLE)

16
IMPACT

Enormous outreach was generated: there were 25.000 visitors to the stand, including different target groups like the general public, professionals, as well as local, regional, national and international experts.

The activity exceeded the expectations. The organisers were continuously in interaction with visitors for 9 days. The visitors were really interested and wanted to be a part of it. Insightful discussions took place about the potential of crops, the conversion techniques, bio-based products, climate issues (replacement of fossil fuels), the degradability of bio-based products, land use, the distribution, where to buy bio-based products, the price, the scale of bio-based production, food vs non-food applications. New professional contacts were made.

17
TOOLS

Quiz, Prezi and a film on bioeconomy

18
COMMUNICATION

During the event a film communicated the professional content, booklets were used to distribute information and short presentations were made to the visiting delegations.

19
METHOD

The main objective was to connect with the public, to present and discuss the perspectives of bioeconomy in order to get an idea about the general level of knowledge, interest, people's questions and concerns. It was an interactive, participatory and collaborative form of research and outreach.

20
STEP-BY-STEP
INSTRUCTIONS

- 1** Find a suitable event for participation – exhibition, conference, fair
- 2** Design the stand
- 3** Develop the storylines
- 4** Gather the materials
- 5** Develop supportive means to explain the information – communication strategy and materials.
- 6** Build the exhibition on location
- 7** Brief the team
- 8** Monitor and evaluate the event

21
LINKS AND PHOTOS

Photo credi:
Britt Roelse,
Wageningen
Research staff

RETROSPECTIVE 2019:
EMBASSY OF SUSTAINABLE
DESIGN

EVALUATION AND REFLECTION

22 LESSONS LEARNED

It is important to speak to visitors, otherwise the messages are too difficult to process.

23

KNOWLEDGE GAIN

Exhibition visitors had largely been unaware of the potentials of bioeconomy and bio-based products and were amazed once they found out more about them. Explanations and discussions can facilitate better understanding, therefore it is important to enhance outreach. The researchers identified the 12 most frequently asked questions, and this might inform communication strategies to reach the general public with the right messages.

24

PITFALLS / OBSTACLES

If there are too many visitors, it is impossible to speak with all of them. Questions emerged on all different aspects of bioeconomy and one expert cannot answer them all.

25

VARIATIONS (IF APPLICABLE)

-

26

TIPS FOR FUTURE IMPLEMENTERS / GOOD-TO-KNOWS

-

27

RECOMMENDATION

-

SHOWCASING BIOECONOMY AT THE MUNICIPALITY OF WAGENINGEN – A LOCAL ACTIVITY

Photos: Wageningen

ACTIVITY HOST / ORGANISER

Wageningen University and Research (WUR), The Netherlands

1 TYPE OF THE ACTIVITY

The activity was developed together with the Municipality of Wageningen, involving the following components:

- ▶ A presentation in the local library
- ▶ Exhibition of panels in a municipality shop – in shopping street
- ▶ Publishing articles in local newspaper

2 FORMAT

Outreach activity

3 THEME / CHALLENGES

The topic of bioeconomy was addressed through discussions and a presentation, as well as articles published in the local paper that is distributed to all inhabitants of Wageningen. The presentation and discussion in the local library, which people could attend with a ticket, were designed to start a dialogue. An exhibition was installed in a municipality shop targeting people passing by in the main shopping street of the City of Wageningen.

4 AIM OF THE ACTIVITY

The aim was to connect Wageningen University Research (WUR) with the inhabitants of the City of Wageningen and to reach out to the general public. People are not aware of WUR's research topics and insights. The topic of bioeconomy is also relevant for local and regional policies on sustainability, waste and circularity.

5 SHORT DESCRIPTION

The activity was part of a larger program which has been developed by the board of WUR and the Municipality of Wageningen; the mayor and the department of sustainability and public affairs were also involved in conceptualization. Different research topics and activities (citizens science, action research, local case studies), relevant for the City of Wageningen, are being conducted in the city. The Library of Wageningen hosted a large part of WUR's local activities which aimed to discuss topical issues with the citizens of Wageningen. WUR's exhibition took place in a municipality shop, which is used as a meeting point on sustainability where people can get advice about sustainable living and housing in Wageningen and functions also as an exhibition space.

6 ORGANIZER TEAM

The outreach activity was developed collaboratively by civil servants, a local politician, and WUR researchers of bioeconomy. Some communication specialists were also involved. One of the Alderman (the chief officer in a district) took part at the opening of the exhibition. To develop the exhibition, a team of 3 researchers and a communication expert worked together, and 10 colleagues were mobilised for hosting the stand.

7 TARGET GROUP

The main target group was the public, the inhabitants of the City of Wageningen. Many students live in Wageningen, who are critical and have interest in sustainable ways of living.

8 CRITICAL NUMBER OF PARTICIPANTS

For the presentation in the library a minimum of 20 participants were targeted. For the exhibition no minimum was set.

9 DURATION

The presentation took place on one occasion (1 hour presentation, 1 hour discussion and drinks reception afterwards). The exhibition lasted for 1 month.

10 PREPARATION PERIOD

1 meeting a week for 2 months. 8 days in total.

11 LOCATION

The event had a central location, in the middle of the city of Wageningen of 45.000 inhabitants, making use of the accessible infrastructure and premises like the library and the city shops. The location of the shop had an added value: it is located in the middle of the Wageningen shopping street. Although the shop has limited opening hours (Wednesdays and in the weekends) but the exhibition panels were positioned so that passers-by were able to see them through the windows.

12 BUDGET AND SOURCES OF FINANCING

8000 EUR for personnel costs and 2000 EUR for materials and information brochures. Altogether 10000 EUR.

13 SETTING AND MATERIALS NEEDED

Existing exhibition, panels, videos, brochures on bioeconomy.

20 STEP-BY-STEP INSTRUCTIONS

The most important step was teaming up with the Municipality and making the collaboration with the University and the Research Centre very operational, exploring different ways of working, informing and presenting, and interacting with citizens.

14
INFORMED CONSENT AND COPYRIGHT ISSUES (IF APPLICABLE)

17
TOOLS

15
OUTPUTS (IF APPLICABLE)

18
COMMUNICATION

16
IMPACT

The activity was organized in close cooperation with the municipality and it contributed to better connections and understanding both ways. The activity took place during COVID, therefore its outreach was not as wide as it could have been otherwise.

The following communication formats were used:

- ▶ A film shown to the audience
- ▶ Exhibition panels communicating content
- ▶ Short presentations at shop
- ▶ Presentation in the local library
- ▶ Information brochure for distribution
- ▶ Article published in the local newspaper

19
METHOD

No specific training was needed in this case. Various activities in a policy – research – society collaboration can be used as inspiration.

21 LINKS AND PHOTOS

Photos: Wageningen Research staff

EVALUATION AND REFLECTION

22

LESSONS LEARNED

It is important to enhance outreach and let people know of what's happening on the campus. It is also important to establish collaboration with the municipality.

23

KNOWLEDGE GAIN

Another reason for enhancing outreach is because people are not aware of the most recent scientific discoveries but as soon as they here about bio-based solution and products they become interested and amazed by the possibility.

24

PITFALLS / OBSTACLES

Covid was an obstacle. Presence at the exhibition was difficult to arrange.

25

VARIATIONS (IF APPLICABLE)

-

26

TIPS FOR FUTURE IMPLEMENTERS / GOOD-TO-KNOWS

Consider variance for different target groups: a discussion e.g. at the library is suitable for those interested and informed; for people with little information about bioeconomy, it is best to reach out to them in the shopping street. Good to target both.

27

RECOMMENDATION

-

MAKER SPRINT

ACTIVITY HOST / ORGANISER

Zentrum für Soziale Innovation (ZSI) and Business Upper Austria, Austria

1 TYPE OF THE ACTIVITY

Maker Sprints in general enable the quick development of ideas or products within only a few days. A five-day design thinking on speed, seeks to condense the traditional and somewhat lengthy design thinking process into a week or under, whilst remaining true to its human-centric imperative. As with design thinking, the process starts and ends with the customer.

2 FORMAT

Sprints are highly interactive and face2face. It is important to enable an eye-to-eye concept, engaging all participants at the same level and excluding any type of judgement of ideas.

3 THEME / CHALLENGES

Innovation, design and new business ideas. Based on a specific problem (e.g. specific side streams from the wood sector that are not utilized yet), the sprint seeks to facilitate discussions in a heterogeneous group of people to find many solutions for a concrete problem.

4 AIM OF THE ACTIVITY

- ▶ To collaboratively create solutions for defined problems.
- ▶ To prototype in order to find different solutions/ideas for a specific problem.
- ▶ To bring together makers and businesses, stakeholders from specific branches, artists and people from other fields with innovative ideas, to initiate/launch new business ideas.

5 SHORT DESCRIPTION

The format is designed to find solutions very fast, often not more than 5 days, with the participation of interested people.

- 1) Problem definition.
- 2) Individuals or groups draft ideas for solutions. Be open for creativity!
- 3) Bring back ideas to groups and discuss. Important not to judge! Have a factual and clear discussion.
- 4) Incorporate input from others.
- 5) Decide which solution suggestions will be developed. It is a collaborative decision. (Attention: it is delicate step, because here it is easy to judge. In this phase the groups decide on one solution.)
- 6) Groups work on different parts of the prototype. Tasks are divided.
- 7) When the prototype is ready, it is tested. Gathering of feedback from others. Evaluation (e. g. asking people on the street). All this happens in a very short time period.

6 ORGANIZER TEAM

At least one moderator is needed. Collaboration with a maker space (such as the Tabaktrafik). Engagement for at least 3-5 days.

7 TARGET GROUP

SMEs, industry and business, designers, maker spaces, researchers, students, start-ups, design students, civil society, artists, tinkerers – basically anyone can be addressed by using this format.

8 CRITICAL NUMBER OF PARTICIPANTS

Team size is between 4-20 people. It should be made up of professionals with different profiles including a moderator, designer, decision maker, product manager, developer, and someone familiar with the domain.

9 DURATION

Four to five days

10 PREPARATION PERIOD

Differs significantly, depending on the experience of the maker space, the moderator, the participants' experience, etc. Invitation and open call for participation should be posted at least one month prior to the event. Talk to the maker space organizer so as to match their makers with your activity! Organizers need to ensure and arrange the facilities, breaks, materials to use for prototype. Calculation of costs needs to be made ahead.

11 LOCATION

Maker space, Fablab or Citylab

12 BUDGET AND SOURCES OF FINANCING

The budget depends on aspects of the collaboration: some makerspaces are free, others might charge. Calculate costs with the breaks (lunch, coffee, etc.) and materials for prototyping and the costs for the moderator, workshop material (paper, pens, post-its etc.).

13 SETTING AND MATERIALS NEEDED

A makerspace providing tools and machines might be needed (depending on the topic of the sprint). A 3D printer might be needed.

14
**INFORMED
CONSENT AND
COPYRIGHT ISSUES
(IF APPLICABLE)**

Clarify motivation of participation and expectations. Make agreements if needed.

15
**OUTPUTS
(IF APPLICABLE)**

Collection of ideas, prototypes, or business plans.

16
IMPACT

New business and design ideas can emerge, as well as new solutions to support circular, sustainable bioeconomy in the region. In the best-case scenario, a new SME is established.

17
TOOLS

Depending on the needs of the participants.

18
COMMUNICATION

Organize a 'Introduction event': present the challenge to the makers. Invite publicly makers, tinkerers, stakeholders using different channels (i.e.. maker space mailing list, poster at the maker space, emails to SMEs).

19
METHOD

Design thinking method is used but internal training on the usage of tools could be needed (depending on the challenge/solution).

20
**STEP-BY-STEP
INSTRUCTIONS**

Day 1

Step 1: Clarify motivation, expectations, roles and possible compensation for makers.

Step 2: problem definition and mapping. The first day is all about understanding the issues that users are facing with in the current system and generally discussing and defining the problems and challenges. You should also use this day to choose a goal for your sprint. You can also recruit users for your later tests.

Day 2

Step 3: ideation and brainstorming for ideas.

If you now fully understand the problem, the group generates and specifies initial ideas. For this step a canvas can be used.

Step 4: decision on prototype, storyboard.

Day 3

Step 5: building the prototype

Create your physical prototype by using things that already exist. Use a 3D printer to create prototypes.

Day 4

Step 6: test and evaluate!

You can find out about the fate of your product based on the answers of your test users. Give users some time to interact with the product, monitor their behaviour, and ask them about their experiences. At the end of the day, you should know what changes you need to make to design a user-centric product.

The Sprint is only as useful as its iteration. You have to summarize your findings and decide on the further course of action, using the insights and data gained in the sprint. These sprints can be done iteratively, thus once you have feedback, you could start another loop of development

21
LINKS AND PHOTOS

Photos: HappyLab Vienna, Prototype Berlin

**EXPERIENCE COLLABORATIVE
MANUFACTURING**

**TOWARDS OPEN BUSINESS
MODELS BUILD-TO-ORDER
FURNITURE**

**OPEN!NEXT: SOCIAL
CHALLENGES IN OPEN HARD-
WARE DEVELOPMENT**

**DETAILED DESIGN SPRINT
GUIDELINE:**

EVALUATION AND REFLECTION

22

LESSONS LEARNED

- ▶ Be prepared to clarify the different roles of the participants.
- ▶ Participants do come from different working environment, thus foster acceptance and positive attitude.
- ▶ Somebody from the maker space will need to foster the 'open approach', so that knowledge is shared, products are co-created: clarify business models with the participants if needed.
- ▶ Good, open-minded spirit and common trust are important, as well as the feeling of being included in a team and to have a good working atmosphere.
- ▶ A location is necessary which allows for creative work, access to tools (e.g. a 3D printer, cutting tools), sufficient amount of material for all participants, and provides an atmosphere that supports teamwork and team building. Sufficient time should be allocated for team building activities and a professional facilitator is needed for using group dynamics effectively.

23

KNOWLEDGE GAIN

At the design sprint all participants exchange ideas and expertise and collaboratively gain new knowledge and find/develop (technical) solutions for specific problems or challenges.

The knowledge gain varies a lot and depends greatly on the project you are facilitating. It could be, for instance, knowledge on the process itself, all way to very concrete things like knowledge on how to handle the tools and machines, ideas and processes related to bioeconomy, etc.

24

PITFALLS / OBSTACLES

- ▶ Be aware that SMEs might have different motivations than makers or stakeholders. Different motivations might lead to different understanding of results and output, as well as business models and compensation. It is very important to clarify the compensation of makers/participants beforehand.
- ▶ There is high communication effort to handle. Do not underestimate this aspect!
- ▶ Group dynamics are very important in such a setting, all voices need to be heard and facilitators need to support introverted participants to speak out.
- ▶ Objectives must be very clear and clear instructions are needed for each session to be able to develop a real prototype.

25

VARIATIONS (IF APPLICABLE)

Depending on the context, the starting point and the specific expected output of the sprint, the concept can be extended or shortened.

26

TIPS FOR FUTURE IMPLEMENTERS / GOOD-TO-KNOWS

This format needs a lot of preparation and a high flexibility on the part of the facilitators during the workshop reacting participants' needs.

As the group needs to develop a prototype together, it is very important that the group builds a strong and trustful team. Plan sufficient sessions and time for group building, including breaks in a comfortable and welcoming atmosphere.

27

RECOMMENDATION

This activity is for you if...

- ... you would like to do something innovative.
- ... you would like to have a result in a very short time.
- ... you are looking for an activity involving a heterogeneous group of people.
- ... you like cooperation.
- ... you have/would like to establish good contacts with a maker space.
- ... you are looking for an activity that works well for SMEs/industry.
- ... you are looking for product/solution development.
- ... you work with creative people that are interested in developing innovative solutions for current challenges society is facing. As the format takes a lot of time, it is necessary to work with participants that have high motivation to solve the respective challenges.

BROWN BAG MEETING FOR POLICY EXCHANGE

Photo: Bing.com

1 ACTIVITY HOST / ORGANISER

Zentrum für Soziale Innovation (ZSI), Austria

1 TYPE OF THE ACTIVITY

Policy loop based on a "brown bag meeting" format.

2 FORMAT

Brown bag meetings are meetings in a more informal setting, where participants bring a light lunch. Thus, participants physically participate in such meetings, although a hybrid format can also be considered. For the policy loop brown bag meeting a light lunch should be prepared by the organisers. Content is presented to the participants in an interactive setting and, as a next step, interactively discussed and validated.

3 THEME / CHALLENGES

This is a format that enables exchange and validation of specific results relevant for policy makers. It is a format that allows for intensive exchange in a comfortable atmosphere in a very tight timeframe.

4 AIM OF THE ACTIVITY

A diverse group of policy makers become familiar with new insights and results related to a specific topic; they bring in their perspectives and together validate the content. Through this format, results are disseminated and an uptake of results by policy makers can be strengthened.

5 SHORT DESCRIPTION

The brown bag meeting is planned over lunch time (or a break time in the afternoon). Snacks and beverages are prepared, such as sandwiches, light finger food, juice, coffee, and tea etc. In this rather informal setting, where a lunch break and a meeting are combined, organisers enable exchange among participants. For a policy specific brown bag meeting, the most important results of the topic of interest must be well prepared and guiding questions help to structure the discussion. A facilitator supports the discussion and takes notes of the most important aspects on a flip chart or a pin wall. Different colours of post-its or moderation cards help to document participants' consents and dissents. The meeting lasts between one and two hours.

6 ORGANIZER TEAM

This format requires a person preparing the room (food, chairs, flip charts/pin walls), and one facilitator, who is responsible for enabling fruitful discussions and taking notes for the group. Project staff will prepare the presentation of results and align with the facilitator the process in the workshop. If any of the colleagues in the team is familiar with meeting moderation, no external facilitators will be needed.

7 TARGET GROUP

Policy makers; multi-stakeholder groups; project teams.

8 CRITICAL NUMBER OF PARTICIPANTS

Depending on the specific goal of the brown bag meeting, between 5 and 15 participants are appropriate in this format.

9 DURATION

A brown bag meeting lasts between one and two hours.

10 PREPARATION PERIOD

This easy format does not require too much preparation. However, the following should be considered: 3 hours may be necessary for the invitation process (start the invitation process at least 2 months prior to the event), 2 hours for preparing the room and food; 2 hours for team preparation with facilitator (agree on clear goal for the meeting, guiding questions, and a way of documentation). 2 hours may be necessary for documenting the results.

11 LOCATION

This activity is a face-to-face activity and is most suitable in urban areas, where participants do not have to travel long distances. It takes place in a sunny, light, and comfortable room, providing enough space for the number of participants. This room must be equipped with at least one table and chairs around. In case small group work is planned, e.g. due to a larger number of participants, bar tables are well suited to enable informal group discussions there.

12 BUDGET AND SOURCES OF FINANCING

This format allows for saving budget. The easy to apply design does not require external facilitation and meeting rooms are often available in-house. However, the food and beverages must be provided.

13 SETTING AND MATERIALS NEEDED

Beamer for presentation, flip chart or pin wall, post-its or moderation cards (+ pins), light meeting room

14 INFORMED CONSENT AND COPYRIGHT ISSUES (IF APPLICABLE)

Clarify motivation of participation and expectations. Make agreements if needed.

15 OUTPUTS (IF APPLICABLE)

E.g. list of validated policy recommendations.

16 IMPACT

The activity leads to awareness raising of specific issues and might support a potential uptake of results by policy makers. Through bringing in their perspectives and discussing the results based on their needs, this uptake is strengthened.

17 TOOLS

-

18 COMMUNICATION

For this activity potential participants are directly contacted and invited via email or phone. The results of the discussion can be disseminated via social media channels. Moreover, the final results, with discussion points integrated, will lead into policy recommendations and/or policy briefs.

19 METHOD

The activity is adapted to the brown bag meeting methodology, where participants bring their lunch bags themselves. However, the advantage of this method is the informal setting allowing for quick and easy exchange and valuable results, the short time schedule and the low costs. Results must be harvested using traditional workshop methodologies and documentation formats on flip charts and pin walls.

20 STEP-BY-STEP INSTRUCTIONS

- 1 Identify policy stakeholders who are most relevant for the exchange and validation process.
- 2 Book a room.
- 3 Send invitations and agenda to policy stakeholders.
- 4 Prepare the location (Important: comfortable, welcoming atmosphere, finger food and beverages on the table, flip charts, pin walls, workshop materials)
- 5 Run the event
 - 5.1. Introduction and welcome
 - 5.2. Short introduction round
 - 5.3. Short information of the process
 - 5.4. Presentation of the topic to be discussed (keep it brief)
 - 5.5. Informal stimulation of discussion
 - 5.6. Structured discussion and validation based on prepared questions
 - 5.7. Documentation on prepared flip chart / pin wall
 - 5.8. Summary and closing
- 6 Documentation
- 7 Email to participants with photo documentation and further steps
- 8 Integrate results in policy briefs and policy recommendations
- 9 Publish result

21 LINKS AND PHOTOS

Photos:
Sport 1 / Imago,
Fellow.app

WHAT IS A BROWN BAG MEETING? DEFINITION, TYPES, AND KEY BENEFITS

EVALUATION AND REFLECTION

22 LESSON LEARNED

The format is easy to apply and not limited to a specific target group. A welcoming atmosphere, nice food and a lively exchange stimulate fruitful exchange and help participants to overcome hierarchical barriers and support a positive group dynamic. It is very good if there are already specific results to be discussed, agreed, or validated. Consents and dissents can easily be documented. However, discussion questions have to be well prepared to get the results needed.

23 KNOWLEDGE GAIN

In the case of working with policy makers, the participants might be familiar with the general topic discussed but gain new knowledge about the new insights presented and reflected here. Moreover, the format aims at strengthening the uptake of policy relevant results by persons with decision-making power.

24 PITFALLS / OBSTACLES

This might be a format some participants might not be used to. It is therefore important to briefly introduce the format already in the invitation (e.g. emphasize that participants have the opportunity to exchange and that organisers provide lunch and beverages, etc.). It is important to ensure a comfortable atmosphere starting from the welcoming of participants throughout the end. In case organisers decide to work with smaller groups, it is important to make sure that the discussions at each table stay focussed.

25 VARIATIONS (IF APPLICABLE)

Brown bag meetings come from the US and are usually applied in internal company teams. However, adapting the concept e.g. for policy exchange, as suggested here, is a good way to stimulate new thoughts and lively discussions. Usually, the meeting takes place around one table. However, the format can be adapted by, for instance, providing several smaller tables and letting small groups of participants discuss different questions at different tables. This is recommended for larger groups.

26 TIPS FOR FUTURE IMPLEMENTERS / GOOD-TO-KNOWS

Be well prepared, be open-minded and trust the power of creative exchange formats.

27 RECOMMENDATION

This activity is for you if...

... you have important results for policy makers you would like to disseminate but also reflect on, bringing in different perspectives.

This format helps you to reach your target group and engage with them on a very high level, and thus improve your policy recommendations before the final dissemination.

SIMULATION DAYS

Photo: Universal Robots

ACTIVITY HOST / ORGANISER

Business Upper Austria in cooperation with Tischlerei Weissengruber, Universal Robotics und Fa. Schmachtl - Austria

1 TYPE OF THE ACTIVITY

Workshop

2 FORMAT

The activity is interactive, and it needs to be carried out in person, since participants operate and program robots themselves.

3 THEME / CHALLENGES

The main challenge of the activity is to show participants how to apply robots in a practical way and through this to support carpenters with digital transition.

4 AIM OF THE ACTIVITY

The aim is to mitigate the uncertainties around the use of robots for several applications in carpentry production.

5 SHORT DESCRIPTION

“Ready to automate your carpentry production? Universal Robots has revolutionized the setup of “Cobots”, reducing setup times previously measured in oodles of time to just a few hours. Universal Robots customers report an average implementation time of only half a day. An untrained user needs unusually little time to support the first simple tasks with the “Cobots”. Attending to the Simulation Day the participants can practice the implementation of the robots by operating them in order to simulate the various possible applications of the “Cobots” in the carpentry industry.”

6 ORGANIZER TEAM

It is necessary to have one facilitator from the organization (in this case Business Upper Austria), who explains and introduces the workshop. It is also necessary to have one or more people from the robotics organization (in this case Universal Robotics), who will demonstrate the “Cobots”, help participants to program it and also be available for answering technical questions. Additionally, it is necessary to have one person from the host organisation (in this case, furniture producer Weissengruber) to welcome everyone and to assess the organization of the workshop.

7 TARGET GROUP

The direct target group is carpenters.

8 CRITICAL NUMBER OF PARTICIPANTS

20 people

9 DURATION

The workshop is four hours long.

10 PREPARATION PERIOD

3 weeks are needed to prepare the event.

11 LOCATION

The location depends on the target group. In the case of the specific activity described, the workshop needs to take place in a carpentry, but it can vary, depending on the addressed industry.

12 BUDGET AND SOURCES OF FINANCING

Financing comes from the participation fees: 90 EUR for Business Upper Austria members and 165 EUR for non-members.

13 SETTING AND MATERIALS NEEDED

“Cobots” – cooperative robots designed for human-robot interactions – are essential equipment for the activity. A screen or projector is needed for a presentation at the beginning of the workshop.

14 INFORMED CONSENT AND COPYRIGHT ISSUES (IF APPLICABLE)

-

15 OUTPUTS (IF APPLICABLE)

Participants can program the “cobots” themselves and see the immediate results and a coding itself. Additionally, the Business Upper Austria team always takes photos and videos of such workshops to share the results in social media and newsletter.

16 IMPACT

In the short- and medium-term, the carpenters might become more interested in and willing to implement robotics in their production as well. In the best-case scenario, they might implement them in the long term.

17 TOOLS

Programming software installed to code and to operate the robots.

18 COMMUNICATION

Before the workshop, direct company visits take place to understand the carpenters’ needs and expectations. Advertise the event on social media and in newsletters. The videos as outputs of the process and photos taken are used in the post-communication.

19 METHOD

20 STEP-BY-STEP INSTRUCTIONS

- 1 Create detailed specifications of the events (cooperation between organisations, workshop locations, potential participants, target group).
- 2 Create the concept of the event together with the cooperating organisations (ask what is possible – can participants really program and tests the “Cobots” in a few hours of the workshop? What is the right location for doing it?)
- 3 Create event webpage in the organisation website.
- 4 Advertise the event, recruit participants.
- 5 Prepare the location.
- 6 Order catering.
- 7 Run the event
 - 7.1. Introductions (meet-and-greet)
 - 7.2. Overview of the event (organizers explain the agenda and introduce the importance of digitalisation)
 - 7.3. Three “Cobots” are installed and put into operation at three production stations.
 - 7.4. Participants can operate the robots themselves.
 - 7.5. Participants can install an add-on themselves.
 - 7.6. Participants can program their first program.
 - 7.7. Participants can discuss the practical applications with experts.
 - 7.8. Organizers conclude the workshop and thank all.
- 8 Through the informal networking part, organizers can get feedback on the workshop.
- 9 After the workshop, make sure to have follow-up communication (publish podcasts, articles, social media posts, follow-up emails etc.) with the success-story of the workshop.

21 LINKS AND PHOTOS

Workshop participants during presentation

Operation of a Cobot

Operation of the second Cobot

Photos: Business Upper Austria

[EVENT WEBSITE WITH MORE INFORMATION](#)

EVALUATION AND REFLECTION

22 LESSONS LEARNED

-

23 KNOWLEDGE GAIN

Participants learned how easy it can be to program a “Cobot” and how useful it can be for their carpentries. This could be a first important step for the digitalization of this sector.

24 PITFALLS / OBSTACLES

-

25 VARIATIONS (IF APPLICABLE)

Variation of target group affects the location of workshop.

26 TIPS FOR FUTURE IMPLEMENTERS / GOOD-TO-KNOWS

Plan extra time for the programming and test part.

27 RECOMMENDATION

-

Photo: Universal Robots

SOLVE³ CONFERENCE:

THE PRICE OF BUILDING

- AFFORDABLE BUILDING WITH ECOLOGICAL, ECONOMIC AND SOCIAL FOCUS

ACTIVITY HOST / ORGANISER

Business Upper Austria in cooperation with AFO Architekturforum Oberösterreich

1 TYPE OF THE ACTIVITY

Educational series of short seminars and presentations

2 FORMAT

The conference was carried out offline, participants had the possibility to interact by answering questions at the end of each presentation and to participate in the networking part.

3 THEME / CHALLENGES

The conference is organised annually, focusing on a new topic every year. The topics are also explored in 3 different dimensions. The last topic of the current conference was: The Price of Building - Affordable Building in Ecological, Economic and Social Focus. Some examples of the talks given: "Parametrically planned timber construction: regional, demountable and ecological"; "reduce, re:use, re:cycle"; "Ideas for the half empty family home"; "From building group project to rental house - metamorphosis of an idea".

4 AIM OF THE ACTIVITY

The goal of the event is to bring different positions and approaches closer together by showing alternatives to the current system.

5 SHORT DESCRIPTION

"How much can we afford? We examine this question from different angles. Lack of resources, price pressure, climate protection - the construction and real estate industry as well as cities and municipalities have to tackle many challenges, but they can also achieve a lot. The "SOLVE³ 2022" event will focus on how we can manage to build responsibly despite all the hurdles. Affordable doesn't just mean financially viable. It is also about social and ecological factors and their quality. The aim of the event is to reveal the different positions to define sustainable solutions. The question is not only what you - the architects, planners, building contractors and housing developers - can contribute, but also what framework conditions politics should create." (From the conference website) The half-day-long event tackles different challenges represented by the invited speakers and experts in a form of various short seminars and plenary lectures. An important part of the event is the open networking part, where the audience can discuss informally the issues and approaches that emerged during the seminars.

6 ORGANIZER TEAM

Main organisers: 1 person per organisation (1 from Business Upper Austria and 1 from AFO); Technical support: 1 person to check sound, screen and change presentations; Moderator: 1; Number of speakers: 6 but not more than 8 to have enough dedicated time for each speaker.

7 TARGET GROUP

The target group varies based on the central theme of the conference but a professional audience is the most suitable for the format. In the current case professionals and industry actors like housing developers, policy makers, architects and planners and executors were addressed.

8 CRITICAL NUMBER OF PARTICIPANTS

The minimum number of the audience is about 20 people (not a strict requirement). There is no maximum number of participants, it depends on the location where the conference takes place.

9 DURATION

Three and a half hours and an open-ended networking part.

10 PREPARATION PERIOD

3 months is needed to prepare the event.

11 LOCATION

An urban space is recommended to provide easy access for all. In the current case, as Business Upper Austria carried out the conference in cooperation with AFO, it took place at the Architecture Forum Upper Austria since it was a good fit to the topic.

12 BUDGET AND SOURCES OF FINANCING

Financing through sponsors and participation fees (90 EUR per participant). Approximate budget size: 7000 EUR

13 SETTING AND MATERIALS NEEDED

Screen and sound system for presentation, enough space for a lot of participants and the networking; catering.

17
TOOLS
18
COMMUNICATION

Before the conference:

- ▶ The event was promoted in social media (mostly LinkedIn) and in newsletters for 2 months prior to the event.
- ▶ An e-mail reminder was sent a few days before the event with the description of the location, parking possibilities, etc.

After the conference:

- ▶ A follow-up report with photos was sent via email to all participants of the event.
- ▶ This report was also made available on the organisation's website.

19
METHOD

The activity does not have a specific methodology although organising a seminar or conference can have specific guidelines linked to different sectors.

20

STEP-BY-STEP INSTRUCTIONS

- 1** Brainstorm in the team about the topic of the event (and in this case, the three dimensions that the topic covers: ecological, economic and social focus).
- 2** Develop the concept, location and agenda with cooperating partners.
- 3** Find sponsors and speakers.
- 4** Create a webpage/sub-page for the event on the organisation's website.
- 5** Start advertising the event, recruit participants.
- 6** Send a reminder to the participants.
- 7** Prepare the location.
- 8** Order catering.
- 9** Run the event (during the whole time there is a person taking photos).
 - 9.1.** Introductions from both organisations (Business Upper Austria and AFO) – meet-and-greet session.
 - 9.2.** Presentation of 6 speakers with short breaks between them and with the possibility for the participants to ask questions.
 - 9.3.** Organizers thank all (especially sponsors) and invite participants and speakers to the buffet and networking session.
- 10** Implement post event communication by follow-up email with photos.

21
LINKS AND PHOTOS

Photos: Cityphoto Pelzl

CONFERENCE SUMMARY
14
INFORMED CONSENT AND COPYRIGHT ISSUES (IF APPLICABLE)

Data protection issues need to be addressed for sharing photos of participants.

15
OUTPUTS (IF APPLICABLE)

Photos and summary of the event that is sent afterwards to all participants and made available on the website.

16
IMPACT

The impact of a conference like this is intangible. Knowledge gain is due to the informative presentations containing new knowledge and discoveries. Otherwise conversations between sector and industry players can be boosted during the networking event but the direct impact is hard to assess.

EVALUATION AND REFLECTION

22 LESSONS LEARNED

The location has to have good parking possibilities and easy access.
A technology check is necessary to see if all equipment is working properly.

23 KNOWLEDGE GAIN

Examples of knowledge gain related to the specific industry:

- ▶ The construction industry is responsible for 38 % of CO₂ emissions - the savings potential is correspondingly high if, for example, buildings are not demolished at the end of their service life, but are instead deconstructed.
- ▶ With parametric planning, a software used to create an equation with many unknowns, that delivers the solution of the equation in an optimal result. In this way, savings can be made already in the planning process, but also in the execution. "The price of building is related to know-how. Optimized construction saves working time and material."

Seminars are suitable for gaining insightful new knowledge and information, this is the most classic and well-established format to gain concrete knowledge and discoveries.

24 PITFALLS / OBSTACLES

Find enough speakers to present for free or for a small fee due to relatively tight budget. Last minute cancellations might present risks

25 VARIATIONS (IF APPLICABLE)

The variation relates more or less to speakers on different topics.

26 TIPS FOR FUTURE IMPLEMENTERS / GOOD-TO-KNOWS

-

27 RECOMMENDATION

-

“SUSTAINABLE AGROFOOD PRODUCTIONS” SUMMER SCHOOL

ACTIVITY HOST / ORGANISER

University of Palermo (UNIPA), Italy

1 TYPE OF THE ACTIVITY

Summer school belonging to educational events within the alliance of the universities FORTHEM

2 FORMAT

Plenary sessions and training, visits to enterprises, simulated activities related to quality assessment of agri-food productions.

3 THEME / CHALLENGES

Fostering multidisciplinary approaches in the frame of sustainable development goals (SDG) 2030 agenda, spanning research in the social sciences, agri-food sciences, food processing and technology, health etc.

4 AIM OF THE ACTIVITY

The current activity is in line with the FORTHEM alliance objectives, as it belongs to the Collective Short-term Mobility Activities, aimed to stimulate new teaching approaches focusing on:

- ▶ innovation of the teaching program (focusing on sustainability in the agri-food system, according to the agenda 2020),
- ▶ feasibility, contents, structure, planned organization,
- ▶ coherence with overall objectives of the FORTHEM alliance (mobility, research and innovation, regional and civic outreach),
- ▶ provisions by organizers to cover organizational costs.

Photo: Concetta Maria Messina

5 SHORT DESCRIPTION

The main topic of the summer school was linked to the necessity to increase sustainability in the food value chain, focusing on all steps, from production to processing and consumption, reducing food loss and waste.

Students were involved in meetings with SMEs, food bloggers, focusing on the utilization of the Mediterranean primary food resources, fruits, vegetables, dairy and fishery products. The Mediterranean diet and gastronomy were discussed and experienced in terms of food management, cooking and communication, including food & beverages (wine and beer). The summer school included a guided visit to the botanical garden, to salt works and to a wine company. Furthermore a “Biodiversity Art Exhibition” by Fondazione Sant’Elia was organised alongside with a performance of the international artist Rafael Yossef Herman.

6 ORGANIZER TEAM / PARTNERS

The organizing team included the participants of the FORTHEM Food Science Lab: 4 professors as staff members (including the project leader), 4 members of the administrative/supporting staff, 4 students from the hosting institution.

The organizational tasks were managed by 5 staff members and 4 students. The workshop was moderated by 2 moderators and the number of invited speakers was 8.

7 TARGET GROUP

The summer school targets Master or PhD students in the field of food sciences and technology or biology. Basic English level was required.

8 CRITICAL NUMBER OF PARTICIPANTS

The number of participating students from the FORTHEM universities alliance was 36. It is possible to increase the number of students, but the programme, location, the budget and the operative effort will also increase significantly.

9 DURATION

5 days during the early summer.

10 PREPARATION PERIOD

The workshop was organized in 6 months.

- ▶ public recruitment of FORTHEM Alliance students,
- ▶ interviews and selection of candidates from hosting institution members,
- ▶ drafting of authorisations for foreign student’s participation,
- ▶ invitation letters to invited speakers,
- ▶ e-mail for the dissemination of the event including the draft of the event.

11 LOCATION

The plenary sessions of the summer school took place in Palermo, at the Department of Agri-food Sciences and Forestry (SAAF) (University of Palermo) and included visits to a winery, an experimental cellar, a visual art exhibition on biodiversity, a visit to saltpans and salt harvesting in Trapani. The locations should be suitable to host the desired number of participants, provide place for lectures and seminars and should be located close to the industry for site visits.

12 BUDGET AND SOURCES OF FINANCING

Organizational costs incurred (on top of mobility and living costs) and sources of funding for general costs (related to the use of onsite infrastructures & resources) was overseen by FORTHEM and provided by local private and public sponsors.

13 SETTING AND MATERIALS NEEDED

Some of the needed materials for the realization of the workshop were: internet connection, laptops, audio and video system, projector and projection screen, conference supplies (notebooks and pens) and brochures.

14 INFORMED CONSENT AND COPYRIGHT ISSUES (IF APPLICABLE)

15 OUTPUTS (IF APPLICABLE)

The outputs of the summer school were a final report created by each participant, a photo catalogue, the creation of a website and social media advertising and creation of a satisfaction survey. Students were awarded credits recognition by an open badge system that lets them use it all around Europe.

16 IMPACT

The desired impact of the FORTHEM program is to promote sustainable development through mobility actions that aim to have impact on the protections of all human rights, freedom of movement within the European Union, individual freedoms, democracy, allowing citizens to enjoy their political, human and individual rights to live without discrimination.

17 TOOLS

The tools used during the activity were PowerPoint (used by the invited speakers and moderators), as well as tools necessary for wine and food tasting (wine-tasting receptacle, plates, etc.).

18 COMMUNICATION

Before the start of the activity, the workshop was promoted through social media, as well as the websites of UNIPA and FORTHEM.

19 METHOD

The summer school was organized by a trained organizing committee responsible for speakers' invitations, contacting the wine company and the botanical garden manager. The committee was also responsible for student's selection and training. Specific content related methods were not implemented.

20 STEP-BY-STEP INSTRUCTIONS

- 1 Create detailed specifications of the event (theme, set up rules and regulations of the event, pick moderators and invite speakers, decide the location, date, crew, decide about the offline, online or hybrid format etc.).
- 2 Find sponsors, press contacts and companies related to the topic.
- 3 Design the image of the event and dissemination platforms.
- 4 Advertise the event, recruit participants.
- 5 Prepare the location.
- 6 Run the event.
 - 6.1. Welcoming (meet-and-greet)
 - 6.2. Overview of the event (organizers explain the summer school agenda)
 - 6.3. Hacking (collaboration on the project in a team format)
 - 6.4. The crew facilitates the life of participants and mentors during the summer school
 - 6.5. The crew creates video and photo documentation, podcast, interviews
 - 6.6. The participants take part in the summer school by active participation to the plenary section (lectures and guided visits)
- 7 The participants present a finished or unfinished work
- 8 Create a satisfaction survey for the stakeholders and evaluate it

Photos: Concetta Maria Messina

[UNIPA'S WEBSTIE](#)

[FORTHEM - SUMMER SCHOOL "SUSTAINABLE AGROFOOD PRODUCTIONS"](#)

[UNIPA FORTHEM SUMMER SCHOOL 2021-2022: A POSITIVE BALANCE](#)

EVALUATION AND REFLECTION

22 LESSONS LEARNED

Participation in the summer school represented an important chance to increase the knowledge of the principal value-chains of the balanced economic growth and price stability, a highly competitive market economy with full employment and social progress, the environmental protection, according to the goal of the agenda 2030.

23 KNOWLEDGE GAIN

The summer school provided a great overview of the status of sustainable agri-food production. During the summer school students were welcomed by the project leader, who presented the staff involved and the program. The main topics discussed were linked to sustainable productions and value-chains, according to the SDGs, particularly: case studies on Mediterranean value-chains and the effects of the COVID-19 on the food value-chains were presented, followed by a guided visit to the botanical garden. Marketing strategies were discussed, linking sustainability with innovation, linking the theoretical information with enterprise's needs. The Mediterranean diet, gastronomy, and communication were reviewed with the participation of representative of enterprises, food bloggers and chefs. The sustainable food processing technology was approached from bottleneck to opportunities for innovation by visit with demonstrative actions, at the laboratory for the sensorial analysis (SAAF). In addition, with the aim to strengthening microbiome across food value-chain to increase health and welfare, blue-based production topic was highlighted since it represents an important sector able to increase aquatic resources sustainability and to meet the SDGs. The plenary session was followed by a visit with demonstrative actions, at the laboratory of microbiology applied to agri-food production. Furthermore, were organized the Biodiversity Art Exhibition by Fondazione Sant'Elia and the performance of the international artist Rafael Yossef Herman, to attest the valuable link between biodiversity preservation, sustainability and art. The summer school format provides the opportunity to gain in-depth understanding of the topics addressed and helps students, participants to engage and start conversations around the central topics.

24 PITFALLS / OBSTACLES

-

25 VARIATIONS (IF APPLICABLE)

-

26 TIPS FOR FUTURE IMPLEMENTERS / GOOD-TO-KNOWS

Additional support from the central organisation in terms of human resources for secretarial work, registration, mail management, etc. might be needed.

27 RECOMMENDATION

Additional support for professional staff dedicated to built-in conference management.

“BEYOND THE HORIZON EUROPE AND GREEN-DEAL: HOW THE « FORTHEM FOOD SCIENCE LAB » COULD CONTRIBUTE TO EU GOALS”

Photo: CHUTERSNAP on Unsplash

ACTIVITY HOST / ORGANISER

University of Palermo (UNIPA), Italy

1 TYPE OF THE ACTIVITY

Workshop on research topics related to the link between the European Green Deal and healthy food system, combined with a match-making event with food industry representatives at European level.

2 FORMAT

Hybrid sessions

3 THEME / CHALLENGES

To identify the main topics related to the Green Deal objectives which focus on “a healthy food system for people and the planet”, and which follow the EU’s main goals in these areas:

- 1) ensure food security in the face of climate change and biodiversity loss,
- 2) reduce the environmental and climate footprint of the EU food system,
- 3) strengthen the EU food system’s resilience,
- 4) lead a global transition towards competitive sustainability from farm to fork.

4 AIM OF THE ACTIVITY

The aim of the workshop is to set state-of-the-art research topics carried out in the different research teams within the Alliance corresponding to the Green Deal objectives and calls.

5 SHORT DESCRIPTION

The main topic of the workshop addressed the major societal challenges relating to food, food production, feeding and health, reflecting the current and future trends in human activity and their relationship to the environment and the links between well-being, health, food habits and education.

6 ORGANIZER TEAM / PARTNERS

The organizing team included the FORTHEM Food Science Lab (University of Palermo) and FIT FORTHEM. The workshop was organized by UNIPA teams with Université de Bourgogne (France). The workshop was moderated by 10 moderators and the number of invited speakers was 25.

7 TARGET GROUP

The workshop targets PhDs and Postdocs, academics and students of the FORTHEM Alliance, as well as representatives from the food industry and non-academic stakeholders.

8 CRITICAL NUMBER OF PARTICIPANTS

The total number of participants as audience at the plenary session was over 50.

9 DURATION

3 days during springtime.

10 PREPARATION PERIOD

The workshop was organized in 3 months. Invitation letters were sent out to stakeholders, project participants and potential speakers and the workshop was advertised on the project and the university website, as well as on social media. The draft of the event agenda, flyers, brochures were created in advance, collaboratively by the staff of the involved universities.

11 LOCATION

The workshop took place at Orto Botanico - Università degli Studi di Palermo in Palermo. It is important to choose a location which has multiple features and can host presentations, roundtable discussion and informal gatherings as well, and fits the style of the event (industrial setting, more classical representative locations).

12 BUDGET AND SOURCES OF FINANCING

The registration to the workshop was free of charge. Organizational costs incurred (on top of mobility and living costs) and sources of funding for general costs (related to the use of onsite infrastructures & resources) was overseen by FORTHEM and provided by local, private and public sponsors.

13 SETTING AND MATERIALS NEEDED

The materials needed for the realization of the workshop were: internet connection, laptops, audio and video system, video projector and projection screen, conferences supplies (notebooks and pens) flyers and brochures.

14 INFORMED CONSENT AND COPYRIGHT ISSUES (IF APPLICABLE)

-

15 OUTPUTS (IF APPLICABLE)

The output of the workshop was a book of abstracts containing 31 scientific abstracts related to quality assessment of agri-food productions, drafted by PhDs, postdocs, academics and students who took part in the event. Furthermore, academic participants (professors, researchers, students) were awarded by credits recognition by an open badge system that let them to use it all around Europe.

16 IMPACT

The impact of the workshop was to identify the main topics able to suit with the EU calls within the Food Science Lab, and to identify new partnerships and consortia to be created.

17 TOOLS

The tools used during the activity were PowerPoint (used by the invited speakers and moderators), as well as tools necessary for wine and food tasting (wine-tasting receptacle, plates, etc.).

18 COMMUNICATION

Before the start of the activity, the workshop was promoted through social media, UNIPA's and FORTHEM's websites. At the end of the event, a photo catalogue was published on UNIPA's website and on project social media.

19 METHOD

The workshop was organized by a trained organising committee responsible for speaker invitations, selecting students' abstracts, keeping contacts with the manager of the botanical garden and all the staff involved. Specific content related methods were not implemented.

20 STEP-BY-STEP INSTRUCTIONS

- 1 Create detailed specifications of the event (theme, set up rules and regulations of the event, pick moderators and speakers, set the location, date, crew, decide on the format (offline, online or hybrid).
- 2 Find sponsors, press contacts and companies related to the topic.
- 3 Design the image of the event and identify the dissemination platforms.
- 4 Advertise the event, recruit participants.
- 6 Prepare the location.
- 7 Run the event.

Agenda of the activity

DAY1 was dedicated to the following scientific sessions:

- SESSION A "Food quality"
- SESSION B "Biotechnology and Biochemistry for food and agriculture"
- SESSION C "Biochemistry and consumer health"
- SESSION D "Biopackaging – Consumer behaviour"

DAY2 was dedicated to the meetings with productive clusters and enterprises of the agri-food sectors. New calls for projects were presented.

DAY3: the FORTHEM Food Science progress meeting took place, followed by a roundtable discussion with all representatives of the Food Labs. An open discussion on the future of the FOOD SCIENCES LAB, based on Research-Innovation-transfer Missions was carried out.

- 7.1. Welcoming (meet-and-greet)
- 7.2. Overview of the event (organizers explain the summer school agenda)
- 7.3. Hacking (collaboration on the project in a team format)
- 7.4. The crew facilitates the life of participants and mentors during the event
- 7.5. The crew creates video and photo documentation
- 7.6. The participants take part to the workshop by active participation to the plenary section (lectures and guided visits)

21 LINKS AND PHOTOS

Photos: Forthem

UNIPA'S WEBSITE

PRESENTATION OF RESEARCH TOPICS RELATED TO A HEALTHY FOOD SYSTEM FOR PEOPLE AND PLANET WITHIN THE FORTHEM ALLIANCE

FORTHEM UNIVERSITY ALLIANCE WEBSITE

EVALUATION AND REFLECTION

22 LESSONS LEARNED

The event represented an important chance to underline the progress of the Food Science Lab and to increase the possible new developments in the next edition of FORTHEM, taking into account the EU food system, looking at the European Green Deal and the EU's sustainable and inclusive growth strategy.

Lesson learned related to the operative aspects can be that a classical scientific activity like the current one should include a variety of formats (roundtables, plenaries, seminars) and entertaining elements to be attractive to the wide range of the target group.

23 KNOWLEDGE GAIN

The Botanical Garden of the University of Palermo hosted the FORTHEM Food Science Lab meetings, as well as the lecturers by UNIPA and FORTHEM Alliance partner universities. Traditional information and knowledge gain can happen during an activity like this, when international actors and multi-sectoral agents can discuss practices in light of future planning and potential collaborations.

24 PITFALLS / OBSTACLES

The workshop occurred in a period of COVID and some participants could not be present.

25 VARIATIONS (IF APPLICABLE)

-

26 TIPS FOR FUTURE IMPLEMENTERS / GOOD-TO-KNOWS

Additional support from the central organisation in terms of human resources for secretarial work, registration, mail management, etc. might be needed.

27 RECOMMENDATION

Additional support for professional staff dedicated to different formats like conference management.

MINNOFEST INNOVATION FESTIVAL

ACTIVITY HOST / ORGANISER

Metropolia University of Applied Sciences, Finland

Photos: YouTube / Metropolia - More Than a University: European Business Administration

1 TYPE OF THE ACTIVITY

Outreach event

2 FORMAT

Interactive, offline

3 THEME / CHALLENGES

The central challenge of the activity responded to the lack of dissemination opportunities for students' MINNO innovation project course work.

4 AIM OF THE ACTIVITY

To disseminate students' MINNO innovation project course work to the public which can enhance collaboration, students' employment, and networking.

5 SHORT DESCRIPTION

Students solve client cases during the 'MINNO Innovation project course' which means a collaborative team project that solves authentic problems by innovating a novel, practical and concrete solution. Every undergraduate takes part in a 10 ECTS innovation project. One project consists of 270 hours of development work and learning per student, normally 4-7 students/team. The challenges arise from labor market needs and the surrounding society. Students, lecturers and tutors from various fields of study cooperate with organizations to create new solutions. The outcome will not be determined in advance: new solutions will be found during the process for the benefit of businesses and customers. The outcome is presented at the MinnoFest.

6 ORGANIZER TEAM

MINNO innovation project course teachers and students.

Photos: YouTube / Metropolia - More Than a University: European Business Administration

7 TARGET GROUP

Students participating in the MINNO innovation project course present their results to the company which provided them a challenge. Teachers and students who did not participate in the course can also come to listen to the outcome and interact with MINNO students. The target group of the activity is, on one hand, the university students and, on the other hand, labor market actors and the wider academic sector.

8 CRITICAL NUMBER OF PARTICIPANTS

15-20 students attending the course plus the audience (at least 10-20 people)

9 DURATION

4 hours

10 PREPARATION PERIOD

The course runs for 2-4 months. The MinnoFest needs a couple of days prep time to send ad out to possibly interested audience (teachers, students, companies, cities, etc.). The physical location needs to be prepared a day before.

11 LOCATION

The location is the school campus lobby in order to ensure visibility and to engage as many academic citizens as possible.

12 BUDGET AND SOURCES OF FINANCING

Non-profit activity. Additional resources might be required for professional innovation teachers to facilitate the MINNO innovation project course and MinnoFest.

13 SETTING AND MATERIALS NEEDED

Students prepare the materials that are needed to efficiently present their outcome. Each student team needs a table, chairs, and electricity power sockets. A big screen is placed at the entrance of the lobby indicating the 'MinnoFest'.

14 INFORMED CONSENT AND COPYRIGHT ISSUES (IF APPLICABLE)

Some MINNO innovation project course challenges might be under the disclosure agreement. In these cases, the MINNO team cannot present their outcome at the MinnoFest.

15 OUTPUTS (IF APPLICABLE)

PowerPoint presentation and, in some cases, product or service prototypes may be produced.

16 IMPACT

"Metropolia's students brought new ideas and viewpoints to the challenge we gave them. We would have never ourselves come up with such fresh solutions and interpretations. I warmly recommend companies to give their challenges to be solved by Metropolia's students. This kind of cooperation is very useful, and we learned a lot."

– Innovation Manager
Juha Lappalainen,
AbbVie Oy

"Innovation projects can, at their best, lead to very useful and practical results. We experienced that with students who created a concept for us for our first blood donor mobile app. The idea was then developed with our professional partner to launch a real product."

– Director,
Communications and
Human Resources,
Willy Toiviainen Finnish
Red Cross Blood
Service

17 TOOLS

-

18 COMMUNICATION

Emails to notify the event participants and to encourage participation.

19 METHOD

Students will get education and training on innovation processes and methods (lectures), which are necessary for them to conduct the activity in student groups.

20 STEP-BY-STEP INSTRUCTIONS

- 1 Find labor market or society collaborators to design the syllabus and the core topic of the course.
- 2 Announce the course using the academic system.
- 3 Announce the MinnoFest day to potential audience.
- 4 MINNO innovation project course teachers discuss the final outcome and the presentation method with each student team prior to the MinnoFest.
- 5 Send out reminders to the potential audience near the MinnoFest day.
- 6 Prepare the premises a day before the MinnoFest.
- 7 Run the event.
- 8 Implement post event communication.

21 LINKS AND PHOTOS

Photos: Metropolia
UAS media bank

INFORMATION ON MINNO® INNOVATION PROJECTS

EVALUATION AND REFLECTION

22 LESSONS LEARNED

The school campus lobby is an ideal place for the MinnoFest, since it is the most accessible point for the potential audience: students and teachers who do not participate in the MINNO innovation project course.

23 KNOWLEDGE GAIN

"The multidisciplinary groups had great ideas, I was impressed that people specialising in culture, wellbeing and technology were able to come up with solutions together efficiently although they had never met before. The teachers really knew how to facilitate innovation."

– *Technical Evangelist Mikko Kasanen, Microsoft.*

"The innovation project was extremely rewarding, with good team spirit playing an important role. The innovation project provided us with concrete results, which may well lead into a real game. Will Rehabool by the Helsinki Hooligans eventually be seen at the new Children's Hospital? Did we inadvertently enter the gaming business? Who knows?"

– *Cultural Management Student Sonja Linkoneva, Metropolia UAS*

The structured collaboration can boost the collaboration between the different sectors and help students to gain knowledge on real life issues and challenges and help labour market actors to seek for multidisciplinary creative ideas.

24 PITFALLS / OBSTACLES

Audience number could be low.

25 VARIATIONS (IF APPLICABLE)

-

26 TIPS FOR FUTURE IMPLEMENTERS / GOOD-TO-KNOWS

Extra effort is needed to attract a high number of audiences outside of the scope of the course.

27 RECOMMENDATION

Make sure to have enough innovation projects (presenters) and interested audience.

CONTINUING EDUCATION: INDOOR AIR QUALITY SPECIALISTS TRAINING

ACTIVITY HOST / ORGANISER

Metropolia University of Applied Sciences, Finland

Photo: Metropolia UAS media bank

1 TYPE OF THE ACTIVITY

Educational activity

2 FORMAT

Hybrid, interactive

3 THEME / CHALLENGES

To educate skilled workforce for the needs of the industry and the society. For example, in the given case, there is currently a lack of indoor air quality specialists.

4 AIM OF THE ACTIVITY

Educate certified indoor air quality specialists.

5 SHORT DESCRIPTION

The indoor air expert personal certification and the preparatory training for it is designed to produce special experts in indoor air issues and in healthy indoor air environment.

6 ORGANIZER TEAM

Experts (lecturers) in construction, chemistry, genetics, microbiology and admin staff.

7 TARGET GROUP

People who want to be indoor air quality specialists.

Requirement for applicants:

- ▶ A higher or lower university degree completed in the field of natural sciences, environmental sciences and environmental health, a previous professional higher education degree or an equivalent degree, or a previous technician's or an equivalent degree.
- ▶ A degree completed in the field of construction does not meet the basic training requirements of the indoor air specialist regulation.
- ▶ At least three years of work experience in research tasks related to the condition of buildings and health hazards

8 CRITICAL NUMBER OF PARTICIPANTS

10-15 people attending the course

9 DURATION

Two weeks

10 PREPARATION PERIOD

6-12 months

11 LOCATION

Classroom, laboratories, and online learning platforms.

12 BUDGET AND SOURCES OF FINANCING

It can be a profit generating activity.

13 SETTING AND MATERIALS NEEDED

Training contents, laboratory equipment and experiment materials

14 INFORMED CONSENT AND COPYRIGHT ISSUES (IF APPLICABLE)

-

15
OUTPUTS
(IF APPLICABLE)

-

16
IMPACT

Certified indoor air quality specialists. Specialists can act as external experts when examining the health conditions of buildings and premises.

17
TOOLS

Digital teaching tools, online learning platform, lab equipment software, and data analysis software

18
COMMUNICATION

Metropolia's website is used to promote the training.

19
METHOD

The coordination effort is required to combine necessary courses into a two-week, intensive training package. Lab experiments are performed in small groups to enhance learning outcome.

20
STEP-BY-STEP
INSTRUCTIONS

- 1** Map and Gap analysis to find the area of lacking specialists
- 2** Calculate the cost of running the intensive training
- 3** Set an admission fee
- 4** Coordinate courses and resources
- 5** Open an application webpage
- 6** Advertise the intensive training
- 7** Select students
- 8** Run the intensive training
- 9** Satisfaction survey
- 10** Issue certificates

21
LINKS AND PHOTOS

Photo: Metropolia UAS media bank

INFORMATION ON METROPOLIA'S INDOOR AIR SPECIALIST (SISA) TRAINING (IN FINNISH)

EVALUATION AND REFLECTION

22 LESSONS LEARNED

If the training includes experiments, the training venue should include laboratories.

23 KNOWLEDGE GAIN

Training participants learn how to assess indoor air quality via chemical, genetical and microbiological experiments.

24 PITFALLS / OBSTACLES

Audience number could be low.

25 VARIATIONS (IF APPLICABLE)

-

26 TIPS FOR FUTURE IMPLEMENTERS / GOOD-TO-KNOWS

It is important to have enough eligible applicants to cover the costs, so try to find a niche field for your training, maybe linked to bioeconomy, where additional expertise is needed, and training can be developed to educate adults.

27 RECOMMENDATION

Conduct Map and Gap analysis to identify the lack of specialists in a certain field and develop an intensive training to train such specialists.

LEGO SERIOUS PLAY SESSION

FOR VISION CREATION WORKSHOP

Photos: lego.com

ACTIVITY HOST / ORGANISER

CLIC Innovation, Finland

5 SHORT DESCRIPTION

The Lego Serious Play workshop is based on a well-elaborated and common method. Hiring a Lego Serious Play licenced instructor to facilitate the workshop is recommended for undertaking this activity. LEGO® SERIOUS PLAY® began as an experimental process designed for guided workshops with adults to prompt dialogue and encourage reflection, as well as develop problem-solving skills and use imagination. However, SERIOUS PLAY® sets like the Starter Kit are also suitable for building critical thinking skills in kids 6+. Each set is designed to enhance different skills, such as reflection and dialogue, which will enhance the workshop experience. This innovative approach to interaction is a valuable asset in both business and education, and it helps participants open up through the approachable medium of play. *source: lego.com*

6 ORGANIZER TEAM

Lego Serious Play Facilitator, support team from staff for event prep. for 3-4 hours face-to-face workshop.

7 TARGET GROUP

Target group can be anyone involved in the ecosystem vision building. Companies, public institutions, regulators, research institutions, universities, etc.

8 CRITICAL NUMBER OF PARTICIPANTS

Can be up to 100 people if managed in several teams. The recommended participant number for one team is 5-10 people.

9 DURATION

3-4 hours

10 PREPARATION PERIOD

1-2 days, depending on the experience of the facilitator. Although gathering the participants might require a month of prep work prior notice, depending on the industry.

11 LOCATION

Facilities where there is enough room to build Legos. More "creative" inspirational environments are recommended. There needs to be enough room to move and also several tables.

12 BUDGET AND SOURCES OF FINANCING

Depending on the location, on average 5.000 EUR with a licenced instructor. The budget depends on the specific case.

13 SETTING AND MATERIALS NEEDED

Lego blocks and sets are needed. Tables are needed for the building. It is recommended to have reflective questions on the wall in the location as reminders (whiteboard, flips, post-it notes).

14
INFORMED CONSENT AND COPYRIGHT ISSUES (IF APPLICABLE)

No copyright issues are involved. The facilitator should be aware of how to use Lego licenced methods & bricks.

15
OUTPUTS (IF APPLICABLE)

Video of the vision story and a written vision statement.

16
IMPACT

An inclusive and creative way to develop a common vision that is easy to remember in the long run.

17
TOOLS

Lego Serious Play methods & bricks

18
COMMUNICATION

Before the workshop, activation messages should be sent out on how to prepare for the workshop, along with calendar invites & e-mails. The messaging depends on the target group. In case of an open workshop, social media can be used for engagement. After the workshop, sharing of the results and the video can also be done on social media.

19
METHOD

20
STEP-BY-STEP INSTRUCTIONS

The following instructions are referring to the method, and not to the organisation of the activity / event itself.

- 1** Welcome and introduction of the day's target (5 min)
- 2** Icebreaker task: Participants will build individually (1 min) a small model using max 5-8 bricks that shows their hopes and/or fears for the day.
- 3** Tap & tell round to share. The facilitator to engage participants in a discussion about how to tackle together the fears during the day (Reflection question).
- 4** Vision building: the first task is to build the vision model (individual task): build a model of desired target stage for a bioeconomy ecosystem (10 min). Put your model on the base plate. Place the ready model on the table.
3 build rounds:
Round 1: (individual): building time 5 min + share 5min (share your own vision build with tap & tell)
Round 2: (together): 5 min + 5 min: place one common board to table. Each participant takes the "agents or elements" from their board to the common board that they think are necessary for the vision to realize. Tap&tell and sharing.
Round 3: (together): 1min + 6 min, reflection round. Take away or add to boards the elements that are missing from the vision story. Tap&tell and share
Round 4: (together): tap & tell story shared by several participants so the story becomes common & shared to all; facilitator can ask different questions to clarify the story
Round 5: 2-3 people share the story by tap&tell method and the story is recorded (video).

5 The vision story is translated into a written format by the team.

21
LINKS AND PHOTOS

Photos: CLIC Innovation

INFORMATION ON LEGO® SERIOUS PLAY®

EVALUATION AND REFLECTION

22 LESSONS LEARNED

More inspirational environments work better for the workshop. Some people might be suspicious of this method, so winning them over is important – there are different ways to tackle that. More heterogenous groups are better to get different viewpoints.

23 KNOWLEDGE GAIN

This is a creative, collaborative, and inclusive way of developing a common vision and sharing views along the way.

24 PITFALLS / OBSTACLES

Some participants might be biased or suspicious of the play element of the method (“children’s play”). This method is a proven method to achieve great results. The method has been developed and researched over 20 years in highly respected universities like INSEAD.

25 VARIATIONS (IF APPLICABLE)

The workshop can be online too if participants have Lego blocks and a computer with camera.

26 TIPS FOR FUTURE IMPLEMENTERS / GOOD-TO-KNOWS

Understanding about the facilitation method is required, so take the course from a licenced facilitator. Keep it simple, do not overcomplicate things.

27 RECOMMENDATION

-

PURPOSE CREATION TOOL

Photo: CLIC Innovation

ACTIVITY HOST / ORGANISER

CLIC Innovation, Finland

Workshop

Online or face to face

The organising force this activity and tool addresses is to define the aims and the purpose behind the action regardless the specific theme or challenge.

Co-create and plan a common future vision and support strategy development. Outcomes: Purpose/vision, goals, values and themes.

Work in one big group to identify common challenges / opportunities. Ask each participant to write their pre-defined challenges / opportunities on post-it notes and to place their stickies on the canvas on the wall. Discuss through the identified challenges / opportunities. Vote or grade the most important ones and select the opportunities that you want to seize together.

In a face-to-face situation: one facilitator
Online: one facilitator and one technical support

7 TARGET GROUP

Key members of the targeted bioeconomy sector/value chain

8 CRITICAL NUMBER OF PARTICIPANTS

10-15 people

9 DURATION

Workshop duration: 2,5-3 hours

10 PREPARATION PERIOD

The event should be scheduled approximately 1,5 months beforehand. A week before the event, send a calendar invitation to all participants with a pre-assignment. Ask participants to be prepared to present their pre-work outcomes at the event. Preparing the canvases, printouts and collecting materials takes about 30 minutes for face-to-face event and about 60 minutes for online.

11 LOCATION

Can be arranged online or face to face. Location itself isn't relevant.

12 BUDGET AND SOURCES OF FINANCING

All materials are open access, without fees. The budget depends on the final format of the workshop (online/offline).

13 SETTING AND MATERIALS NEEDED

For the face-to-face workshop (30 min): canvases, worksheets for all participants, other workshop materials
For an online workshop (60 min): prepared online boards needed

14 INFORMED CONSENT AND COPYRIGHT ISSUES (IF APPLICABLE)

No copyright issues. Creative Commons licence should be mentioned when this method is used.

15 OUTPUTS (IF APPLICABLE)

The ecosystem purpose and it's goals, values and themes on canvases.

16 IMPACT

Inclusive and visual way to develop a common purpose collectively. Likely to increase stakeholders' commitment.

17 TOOLS

Face-to-face: Printouts of the Ecosystem creation canvas (A1 or A0 for the walls), and A4 for individual work (worksheets).
 Online setting: online boards using e.g. Miro or 4 sectional boards using e.g. Padlet (one board for each segment of the Purpose Creation Canvas) + one full ppt canvas for the use of the workshop assistant

18 COMMUNICATION

The event should be scheduled approximately 1,5 months before the event.
 A week before the event send a calendar invitation to all participants with a pre-assignment. Ask participants to be prepared to present their pre-work outcomes at the event.
 Document the defined common purpose and themes of common interest and share the summary document with the participants.

19 METHOD

Check out the website with the open-source toolbox

20 STEP-BY-STEP INSTRUCTIONS

The following instructions are referring to the method and workshop process not to the organisation of the activity / event itself.

- 1 Define common values (what are the values we stand for?)
- 2 Discuss and define themes of common interest (what topics are we interested in solving together?)
- 3 Agree on common goals (what do we want to achieve together?)
- 4 Summarize the common purpose (why we are here working together?)
- 5 Document the defined common purpose and themes of common interest and share the summary document with the participants.

21 LINKS AND PHOTOS

Photos: CLIC Innovation

Photos:
YouTube /
CLIC Innovation

EVALUATION AND REFLECTION

22 LESSONS LEARNED

-

23 KNOWLEDGE GAIN

-

24 PITFALLS / OBSTACLES

-

25 VARIATIONS (IF APPLICABLE)

-

26 TIPS FOR FUTURE IMPLEMENTERS / GOOD-TO-KNOWS

-

27 RECOMMENDATION

-

LIFELONG LEARNING FESTIVAL

Photo: Aontas

ACTIVITY HOST / ORGANISER

This activity is organised by various organisations, in different countries and at European level like the organisations EAEA is a member in: LLL Week – LifeLong Learning Week, Brussels, European level by Lifelong Lifelong Learning Platform or Adult Learners' Festival, Ireland by AONTAS – National Adult Learning Organization

1 TYPE OF THE ACTIVITY

A learning festival is composed of various activities: awards, workshops, demos, boot camps, expo and fair-like activities, information sessions, lectures, social theatre, performances.

2 FORMAT

- ▶ Interactive and plenary sessions
- ▶ Hybrid, with activities spanning across days or weeks

4 AIM OF THE ACTIVITY

- ▶ To raise awareness, and promote the value, of lifelong learning, which is the first condition to improve access to education for all.
- ▶ To celebrate and champion adult learners and training providers.
- ▶ To promote opportunities, initiatives and projects for lifelong learning.
- ▶ To support sharing ideas and exchanging between policymakers, providers and learners.
- ▶ To reinforce existing partnerships in the ALE/LLL system.

5 SHORT DESCRIPTION

A learning festival aims to raise awareness on learning and education capacity in modern society, as tool of social inclusion, citizenship and personal and professional development, for all citizens. Learning festivals are community-based activities that connect actors at local, national or even international level. The core purpose is to bring together all the actors of the learning and education community (learners, educators, providers, practitioners, policy makers, research etc.) in shared activities, to learn and discuss together about a specific topic or about learning itself.

3 THEME / CHALLENGES

- ▶ The global theme of the learning festivals is adult learning, lifelong learning and adults' participation in learning, and their promotion and celebration.
- ▶ A specific theme or focus can be chosen for each edition (yearly), including transversal topics (for example funding, quality of learning, sustainability of the education system, attractiveness of LLL etc.) or specific subject topics (for example, literacy, life skills, well-being, digital skills, green skills etc.).

6 ORGANIZER TEAM / PARTNERS

- ▶ For a learning festival production, a core team of at least 3-4 people, working a few hours per week along the year, for the programme preparation and contacts with the organiser of specific activities, with a more intense schedule in the days of the festival.
- ▶ The team is usually composed of a coordinator/project manager, a director, community manager/business developer and a communication specialist/manager.
- ▶ Depending on the size and geographical extension (for example for a national learning festival), the team can be also supported by other profiles (event assistant/s, communication officers, administrator etc.).

7 TARGET GROUP

All the actors of the learning and education community, such as learners, educators, providers, practitioners, policy makers, research.

8 CRITICAL NUMBER OF PARTICIPANTS

As many people as can be reached

9 DURATION

The whole festival duration is usually one week. Stand-alone activities can be also organised in other periods, for example for an award or linking to another relevant event.

10 PREPARATION PERIOD

The preparation period is a year long, with organisation activities concentrated to 2-3 months before the festival.

11 LOCATION

- ▶ Public and private space accessible to public, in urban and non-urban settings.
- ▶ Locations of the organisers of the festival and of the organisers of each specific activities
- ▶ Locations offered by partners and sponsors, both private and public entities.

12 BUDGET AND SOURCES OF FINANCING

- ▶ A learning festival is a free of charge activity for participants.
- ▶ The organiser needs to foresee at least a basic budget for the core team and for communication and promotion activities.
- ▶ A crucial factor is the involvement of partners' and sponsors, for example local and national authorities offering their support in promotion and locations and private sponsors offering services, such as technical support, catering, travels, tools and demos etc.
- ▶ Activities of a learning festival are usually offered by their specific organiser and they can be part of larger initiatives (synergies among the festival and existing projects and initiatives is also very important in fact).

13 SETTING AND MATERIALS NEEDED

14 INFORMED CONSENT AND COPYRIGHT ISSUES (IF APPLICABLE)

15 OUTPUTS (IF APPLICABLE)

- ▶ A report is also a common output, for which a light and summary-like approach is advised
- ▶ Articles and news before and during the activities are important as well.

16 IMPACT

The learning festivals support the global and shared understanding of the intrinsic importance of learning and education in our lives and society, for all and for any purpose, for personal and professional development and also just for fun and interest. Learning festival have activities that can be of interested and accessible to any citizens, in any role and capacity.

17 TOOLS

18 COMMUNICATION

A learning festival would require a communication strategy similar to any live activity or event. This varies greatly depending on the size and scope of the activities. It is advised to seek partnerships and sponsorships to support a wider campaign, before, during and after the festival.

19 METHOD

20 STEP-BY-STEP INSTRUCTIONS

Develop a coherent core programme around a central strong theme/topic and then open the festival to registration of activities for stakeholders in the field, either free or by application/selection, with a model by levels, for example core events, partners' events, events around the topic in the context/country linked to the festival etc. See this example:

Are you planning to hold an event for the adult learners by AONTAS

21 LINKS AND PHOTOS

Photos: Enovickea, Aontas

LLLWEEK - LIFELONG LEARNING WEEK, BRUSSELS, EUROPEAN LEVEL

LIFELONG LEARNING WEEKS, SLOVENIA

ADULT LEARNERS' FESTIVAL, IRELAND

FESTIVAL OF LEARNING, UNITED KINGDOM

EVALUATION AND REFLECTION

22 LESSONS LEARNED

23 KNOWLEDGE GAIN

Knowledge gain is one of the main purposes of a learning festival, at least at the general level of learning and knowing more about learning and knowledge. A large variety of specific learning outcomes are possible, depending on the specific topics of the activities composing the festival.

24 PITFALLS / OBSTACLES

- ▶ Maintaining coherence of the overall programme, aligned with the main theme, and high quality of all the activities may be a challenge.
- ▶ The activity depends heavily on collaboration and external support and on the renewal of partnerships and support for every edition.

25 VARIATIONS (IF APPLICABLE)

- ▶ Many variations of the activity are possible, with hybrid formats.
- ▶ The length may vary from 1 day to 1 week and longer, with activities spread across several weeks.

26 TIPS FOR FUTURE IMPLEMENTERS / GOOD-TO-KNOWS

- ▶ The core aspect of a learning festival is that it has to be organised and developed by the same people that will participate.
- ▶ Building a core network of partners, sponsors and possibly co-organisers is a fundamental step.
- ▶ It is also important to link the festival and its programme to existing initiatives and projects, and also to relevant policies and strategic plan, in the context of relevance.

27 RECOMMENDATION

This activity is for you...

- ▶ if you have as main purpose to work on a community-based activity focusing on awareness raising and you wish to involve and address a large part of that community, as organiser and participants.
- ▶ if you have an initial capacity to support the core team preparatory work.
- ▶ if you have an established network of potential partners, sponsors and co-organiser, whose size and potential depends on the scope and size of the festival you intend to develop.

EPALE PODCAST

EPALEPODCAST

Photo: Epale EU

ACTIVITY HOST / ORGANISER

European Association for the Education of Adults (EAEA) (and other organisations) on behalf of the European Commission within a service contract for the Electronic Platform for Adult Learning in Europe (EPALE)

1 TYPE OF THE ACTIVITY

Podcast – short, online, interview-like panel conversation

2 FORMAT

Online

5 SHORT DESCRIPTION

A series of podcasts from adult learning experts to broaden knowledge and expand understanding of various adult learning topics and themes.

3 THEME / CHALLENGES

Podcasts can address any topic related to adult learning, for example, the role of empathy in education for adults; public libraries as learning communities; ALE and skills; adult education and human rights.

4 AIM OF THE ACTIVITY

Share general information and testimonial-like perspectives around a topic, with a conversational approach (like in a TV panel).

6 ORGANIZER TEAM

Content coordinator, moderator/facilitator, sound technician (recording and editing), communication/content editor (publishing and promoting).

7 TARGET GROUP

Any audience interested in getting a general idea of a topic from experts and other participants.

8 CRITICAL NUMBER OF PARTICIPANTS

-

9 DURATION

20-30 minutes

10 PREPARATION PERIOD

- ▶ Program to be organised over months.
- ▶ Identifying and contacting potential speakers for each podcast at least 2 months before the podcast release date.
- ▶ A few hours are needed to prepare each podcast: outline and questions; preparatory meeting with speakers; moderator preparation.
- ▶ A few hours are needed to record and edit the podcast and publish it.

11 LOCATION

- ▶ The podcast is published online, on a sound streaming portal or on a website providing an audio player.
- ▶ A studio-like setting is needed to record it.

12 BUDGET AND SOURCES OF FINANCING

- ▶ The podcasts are free of charge for the audience.
- ▶ The costs are covered by the European Commission as part of the EPALE service.
- ▶ In general, a podcast is a low-cost activity and speakers are not paid. Streaming, storage and audio editing and studio cost may emerge.

13 SETTING AND MATERIALS NEEDED

- ▶ A studio-like setting for recording, to ensure good audio quality.
- ▶ Basic recording technology (microphone, digital recorder or software).

14 INFORMED CONSENT AND COPYRIGHT ISSUES (IF APPLICABLE)

- ▶ Consent is needed from speakers, and it is collected through a custom form.
- ▶ Rights of use of the content must be included in the consent, for all the intended use and organisations.

15 OUTPUTS (IF APPLICABLE)

-

16 IMPACT

The impact is potentially wide, since a podcast is a very easily accessible content, from a variety of devices and in any set up and with short time at disposal. The general impact is to improve awareness around the core topics for a large audience of non-experts in the matter.

17 TOOLS

Basic audio editing tools (available also as free tools)

18 COMMUNICATION

The podcast must be published on a stable location and the series must be promoted regularly through the channels the producer uses for any other communication. It is advised to have a regular publishing schedule and to promote each release through some teasers on social media as well.

19 METHOD

It is good for a podcast series to maintain a certain coherence of format and structure. An outline like a structured interview for a panel discussion is usually applied.

20 STEP-BY-STEP INSTRUCTIONS

- 1 Set up the conceptual background of the podcast series.
- 2 Set up the technical background of the podcast series (storage, streaming platform etc).
- 3 Select the list of topics.
- 4 Find a studio and involve technicians.
- 5 Engage speakers and plan ahead (invitations letters, preparatory meetings, provide list of questions).
- 6 Implement the defined communication steps to gather the audience.
- 7 Schedule the discussion.
- 8 Manage the post-production.
- 9 Publish the episode.

21 LINKS AND PHOTOS

Photos: European Commission, EPALE EU, EPALE Magyarország, EPALE Slovensko, Daniel Lloyd Blunk-Fernández on Unsplash

EVALUATION AND REFLECTION

22 LESSONS LEARNED

A series of podcasts needs to have a regular release schedule and a coherent format, to engage and maintain its audience.

23 KNOWLEDGE GAIN

A podcast is usually oriented to a general knowledge gain on the topic of each release.

24 PITFALLS / OBSTACLES

It may be challenging to maintain quality and the interest of the audience in the long term.

25 VARIATIONS (IF APPLICABLE)

- ▶ Different lengths are possible, up to 1 hour.
- ▶ The release frequency can vary: it can be once per week or once per day, such as the case with talk shows.

26 TIPS FOR FUTURE IMPLEMENTERS / GOOD-TO-KNOWS

- ▶ Plan a medium/long term programme.
- ▶ Select topics linked to actuality.
- ▶ Survey the audiences on new topics for future podcast, for example through a quick poll on the website hosting the podcast or through your regular audience and stakeholders.
- ▶ Engage as diverse speakers as possible, in terms of background, role and geographical context.

27 RECOMMENDATION

This activity is for you if...

- ▶ ... you wish to reach a large audience, with a low-cost budget, while still providing content with an added value.
- ▶ ... you wish to focus on sharing the voices and perspectives of experts, stakeholders or any other group.
- ▶ ... you wish to propose a dynamic format for knowledge sharing to your audience.

CITIZEN SCIENCE ACTION

Photo: .ecsa.ngo

ACTIVITY HOST / ORGANISER

Bay Zoltán Nonprofit Ltd.
for Applied Research

1 TYPE OF THE ACTIVITY
Our citizen science action was a campaign which included communication and educational elements.

2 FORMAT
Citizen science is a participatory activity, in which citizens participate in various scientific and monitoring activities¹. Participants usually support scientists in data collection, via online applications.

3 THEME / CHALLENGES
In our previous citizen science action, we measured the water quality of the Danube, with families, school groups and enthusiastic citizens. Although it was not bioeconomy-related, good subjects can be found for the purposes of the Engage4BIO project as well.

4 AIM OF THE ACTIVITY
Citizen science activities are suitable for involving citizens in different research activities and making them engaged in certain issues. It also has training and educational elements, as participants are trained on how to make the experiments and receive information about a certain subject.

5 SHORT DESCRIPTION
“Research involving citizen science can take many forms, and the roles of the participants can include, for example: identifying a research question; collecting or analysing data to support or refute a hypothesis; monitoring environmental or health conditions for management or policy outcomes; and the creation of generic data within a domain to support a wide range of research questions (such as digitising art collections, observations, or mapping). Activities can also include inductive and exploratory approaches that are based on qualitative knowledge production. In a citizen science project, it can be appropriate to focus exclusively on some of these activities (e.g., only hypothesis-driven) in specific contexts, for example when this is required by funding agencies”².

6 ORGANIZER TEAM
Implementing a good citizen science action requires a complex team:

- ▶ A research team: to build the hypothesis, formulate the research question, find out how citizens can be involved,
- ▶ IT team: to create a data collection platform (application, webpage),
- ▶ A promotion and engagement team: to carry out promotion and engagement activity,
- ▶ A data analysis team,
- ▶ Back-up: to answer questions and solve problems.

 The whole team is coordinated by the scientific lead or a project manager.

7 TARGET GROUP
The target group of the activity is the general public.

8 CRITICAL NUMBER OF PARTICIPANTS
It depends on the available resources. Larger programs can attract thousands of citizens.

9 DURATION
It depends on what kind of data is collected. At least a couple months are needed to gather enough data, but programs can run for years.

10 PREPARATION PERIOD
Preparatory activities are key. Large-scale activities require months of preparation.

11 LOCATION
The location depends on the discipline and the activity. In the project we took part in previously³, measurements were taken at riverbanks.

12 BUDGET AND SOURCES OF FINANCING
Good and large-scale projects need resources. The main elements to be covered are:

- ▶ costs of the staff involved,
- ▶ costs of the data collection platform,
- ▶ special equipment may be needed for experiments,
- ▶ promotion costs.

 There are some open calls to cover these costs, such as the IMPETUS project.

¹M.Haklay et al (2021): Contours of citizen science: a vignette study. R. Soc. Open Sci. Volume 8, Issue 8, pp 1-24. (doi: <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsos.202108>)
²Source: ECSA's characteristics of citizen science. Version 1, April 2020
³<https://drinkablerivers.org/>

13 SETTING AND MATERIALS NEEDED

It depends on the activity. In our previous project, Drinkable Rivers, a complex measurement kit was provided. Additionally, a manual and a video guide were prepared on how to use the kit.

14 INFORMED CONSENT AND COPYRIGHT ISSUES (IF APPLICABLE)

Citizen science has its own standards. Please check the 10 principles of citizen science in the document referenced earlier. Special attention is needed if children take part in the activities.

15 OUTPUTS (IF APPLICABLE)

The tangible output is usually the dataset collected by the participants.

16 IMPACT

- Contribution to scientific research,
- raising awareness of different subjects or disciplines,
- engagement through involvement.

17 TOOLS

The most important tool: data collection platform (application, website, etc.)

18 COMMUNICATION

Active promotion is needed to attract participants. Social or traditional media (such as TV, radio) are the most appropriate channels to reach a wide range of people. After the data analysis, participants need to be informed about the results.

19 METHOD

-

20 STEP-BY-STEP INSTRUCTIONS

- 1 Identify the subject and the methodology.
- 2 Find resources.
- 3 Create data collection platform or get licence for an existing one.
- 4 Finetune the methodology, buy equipment (if necessary), create descriptions, background materials, manuals and/or videos.
- 5 Start promoting the activity to attract citizens.
- 6 Start data collection campaign.
 - 6.1. Make sure that questions are answered – maybe create a FAQ page.
 - 6.2. Support your “citizen researchers” as much as possible.
 - 6.3. Keep promoting.
 - 6.4. Create community (social media groups, etc.)
- 7 Finish data collection.
- 8 Start data analysis.
- 9 Widely disseminate the results. Although they are scientific results, create easily understandable material for the citizen scientists.
- 10 Keep the community engaged.

21 LINKS AND PHOTOS

Photos: Bay Zoltán Nonprofit Kft.

[CONTOURS OF CITIZEN SCIENCE: A VIGNETTE STUDY](#)

[WEBSITE OF THE EUROPEAN CITIZEN SCIENCE ASSOCIATION](#)

EVALUATION AND REFLECTION

22 LESSONS LEARNED

- ▶ Do it well or don't do it! There are so many excellent initiatives, the competition is high.
- ▶ Be as precise and detailed as possible regarding the experiments/data collection.
- ▶ Allocate enough time for the preparation.
- ▶ Be responsive.

Illustration:
ecsa.ngo/annual-report

27 RECOMMENDATION

This activity is for you if....
 ... you need large amount of data for your research. Keep in mind, however, that it is not enough to just "use" your citizen researchers: engagement means a lot more. Keep them involved, build a community!

23 KNOWLEDGE GAIN

24 PITFALLS / OBSTACLES

25 VARIATIONS (IF APPLICABLE)

26 TIPS FOR FUTURE IMPLEMENTERS / GOOD-TO-KNOWS

Illustration: Avril Orloff/theworldcafe.com

WORLD CAFÉ METHOD

ACTIVITY HOST / ORGANISER

Bay Zoltán Nonprofit Ltd.
for Applied Research

1 TYPE OF THE ACTIVITY

The World Café is an interaction method focused on conversations. A Café Conversation is a creative process for leading collaborative dialogue, sharing knowledge and creating possibilities for action in groups.

2 FORMAT

Although it starts with a short plenary, afterwards it is a very interactive method, based on conversations. It can be organised online, if necessary, but the best is the offline setup.

3 THEME / CHALLENGES

It is suitable for brainstorming, sharing opinions, or debating. However, it is not the best tool for complex tasks, such as visioning or strategy building, although this format can feed into the latter or help examine a certain aspect of it. Our activity in 2019 was called: Open Innovation World Café - Climate Innovation and Bioeconomy.

4 AIM OF THE ACTIVITY

Our previous activity was aimed at brainstorming about how Budapest can turn into a liveable city and examining what an individual citizen can do for a more circular economy.

5 SHORT DESCRIPTION

The basic model of the work café method consists of 5 steps:

- 1) Setting: Create a café-like environment.
- 2) Welcome and introduction: The host begins with a warm welcome and an introduction of the World Café process, setting the context, sharing the Café Etiquette, and putting participants at ease.
- 3) Small-Group Rounds: Conversational rounds last from 20 to 30 minutes. At the end of each round, one person remains at each table as the host, while the other 3-4 travels to separate tables.
- 4) Questions: each round is prefaced with a question specially crafted for the specific context and desired purpose of the World Café.
- 5) Harvest: After the small groups, individuals are invited to share insights or other results from their conversations with the rest of the large group. (Source: <https://theworldcafe.com/key-concepts-resources/world-cafe-method/>)

6 ORGANIZER TEAM

- ▶ Depending on the number of participants, several organizers are needed, who act as table hosts. (According to the literature, it is possible that table hosts are volunteers from the participants, but we found it better to use our own staff for this.)
- ▶ There must be one main host who leads the “Welcome and Introduction” session.
- ▶ Engagement required: pre-reading about the method and the questions, active participation during the event, sending notes if they are not collected during the event.

7 TARGET GROUP

The target group is the public. Enthusiastic citizens can be involved in this activity.

8 CRITICAL NUMBER OF PARTICIPANTS

At least 3 tables need to be filled, which means 9-15 participants + 3 table hosts. The maximum number of tables is limited by the available space. If there are too many tables, the “Harvest” part will last too long.

9 DURATION

Half a day

10 PREPARATION PERIOD

The preparation period takes a minimum of 3 weeks and involves the following steps:

- ▶ Set the theme, find a venue and set a time and date.
- ▶ Invite participants – social media channels can work well.
- ▶ The questions asked are critical: spend enough time to find the most appropriate questions. It can be even a single question discussed at each table or there can be several, related questions.
- ▶ Prepare your table hosts.

11 LOCATION

Easily accessible, where a café-like milieu can be created. It can be even a real café. Enough place is needed for the tables. It is advisable to have coffee/tea and snacks available.

12 BUDGET AND SOURCES OF FINANCING

Budget is needed to cover:

- ▶ renting a suitable space,
- ▶ offering coffee/tea and snack,
- ▶ running a social media campaign to attract participants,
- ▶ covering staff costs of hosts and table hosts.

13 SETTING AND MATERIALS NEEDED

-

14 INFORMED CONSENT AND COPYRIGHT ISSUES (IF APPLICABLE)

Consent is needed if:

- ▶ participants' personal data is collected (i.e. attendance sheet is prepared, or after-event e-mails are foreseen to be sent),
 - ▶ photos are taken.
- In our practice, seeking informed consent is usually part of the registration link and/or the attendance sheet.

Illustration: Avril Orloff/theworldcafe.com

15 OUTPUTS (IF APPLICABLE)

-

16 IMPACT

Outcomes may feed into a vision or a strategy document.

17 TOOLS

-

18 COMMUNICATION

Social media is a good channel to reach potential participants and promote the event. In our case, a Facebook campaign was prepared for the event.

19 METHOD

The recommended activity is a method itself.

20 STEP-BY-STEP INSTRUCTIONS

- 1 Define the subject and set the date.
- 2 Find a venue, organise catering.
- 3 Promote the event, recruit participants.
- 4 Find table hosts.
- 5 Define the most appropriate questions.
- 6 Prepare the location.
- 7 Run the event.
 - 7.1. welcome and introduction: setting the context, describing the methodology and the etiquette,
 - 7.2. discussion rounds at the tables,
 - 7.3. table hosts take notes or participants write down their ideas or opinions,
 - 7.4. Harvest: table hosts summarize the main points.
- 8 Collect feedback forms.
- 9 Implement post event communication (social media posts, articles)

21 LINKS AND PHOTOS

MORE ON THE WORLD CAFÉ METHOD

THE WORLD CAFÉ - HOSTING TOOLKIT

Photos: Artofhosting, MSP Guide

EVALUATION AND REFLECTION

22 LESSONS LEARNED

- ▶ This method can be implemented quite easily.
- ▶ There are good supporting materials available.
- ▶ The key to success is good questions and good table hosts.
- ▶ An event targeting the public should not be organised in the morning – after working hours is better.
- ▶ A cosy environment is important.

23 KNOWLEDGE GAIN

In our previous case, some common points came up in the discussions, such as the fact that good practices exist but they are fragmented.

24 PITFALLS / OBSTACLES

Some participants had different expectations from the event and did not like the method. In the evaluation form it was written that they did not gain anything from the discussion.

25 VARIATIONS (IF APPLICABLE)

-

26 TIPS FOR FUTURE IMPLEMENTERS / GOOD-TO-KNOWS

-

27 RECOMMENDATION

-

WATER EDEN

ACTIVITY HOST / ORGANISER

Moholy-Nagy University of Art and Design Budapest in collaboration with Medence Group

Photos: Antal Bodóczy

1 TYPE OF THE ACTIVITY

Interactive outreach activity, as part of an awareness raising art campaign

2 FORMAT

Analogue interactive installation

3 THEME / CHALLENGES

Promoting recycling and the importance of clean and accessible water

4 AIM OF THE ACTIVITY

To broaden the concept of upcycling by recycling Henri Rousseau's painting motifs (not paraphrasing but recycling motifs). To produce a "landmark" and a conversation piece using analogue interaction with playful community-building elements. The installation also aimed to raise awareness of the dominance of virtual reality.

5 SHORT DESCRIPTION

The activity can be described as an unconventional awareness raising activity, using a playful, artistic installation as a tool. The central theme is organised around recycling as a phenomenon and symbolizes it through the reusing act of an art piece for an unrelated purpose. Using water as one of the core elements is also a gesture towards awareness raising about the accessibility of water sources and about the unquestioned access during summertime in light of the climate crisis. The installation also promotes off-grid and offline solutions, the power of tangibility and participation in the over-digitalized realm of the 21st century. The given activity can serve as an inspiration for a creative, public-friendly display of bioeconomy underlining the framework of outreach which is promoting the cause through a bigger event (in this case, the popular, one-week music festival, SZIGET), using the well-established infrastructure of the event.

6 ORGANIZER TEAM

One art director and a concept lead with the involvement of 10-12 MOME Media Design Students. 1 person dealt with communication, management, administration using the framework of Sziget Festival.

7 TARGET GROUP

Wider audience (in the current case, festival audience), the general public

8 CRITICAL NUMBER OF PARTICIPANTS

1 person can use the installation but more the merrier

9 DURATION

1 week (the duration of Sziget Festival)
Summertime is ideal for the implementation

10 PREPARATION PERIOD

2 months, including conceptualization, production and implementation

11 LOCATION

Festival or a bigger hosting event to reach a wider audience

12 BUDGET AND SOURCES OF FINANCING

The activity was financed by Sziget Festival Budapest 2500 EUR for materials. Voluntary work was also involved, compensated by a ticket to the festival.

13 SETTING AND MATERIALS NEEDED

Installation-specific materials:
 ▶ Water pipes, taps, water pump for recycling water
 ▶ Painted plywood, pine slats and beams, metal fasteners and axles.
 Lights and reflectors for evening visibility
 Tent for demonstrators for shading
 The installation is 4x3 square metres and 3 metre high. To install it, an outdoor area of 50 square metres is ideal and additional space/workshop is needed for the preparatory works.

14
**INFORMED
CONSENT AND
COPYRIGHT ISSUES
(IF APPLICABLE)**

The name of creators must be displayed on the spot to communicate copyright and IP.

15
**OUTPUTS
(IF APPLICABLE)**

The installation itself is an output, which can be dismantled and assembled elsewhere.

16
IMPACT

- ▶ This unique format turned out to be an effective tool to start new cooperations and to grab the interest of bigger companies to promote their sustainability visions through art
- ▶ The target audience could learn about the importance of water and recycling in a playful way
- ▶ The message is important, and people reacted to the message
- ▶ For the creators, it is a reference for future works
- ▶ Reached approx. 2000 people

17
TOOLS

Power tools, Photoshop and projector for the creation

18
COMMUNICATION

The communication was linked to the central communication of Sziget Festival. Only a short introduction was created but the festival PR and marketing team was responsible for pre- and post-communication. At the festival location the installation spoke for itself.

19
METHOD

-

20
**STEP-BY-STEP
INSTRUCTIONS**

- 1** Finetuning the message jointly with the partners
- 2** Finding a hosting event - festivals and bigger events are best to have great outreach
- 3** Clarifying the target audience
- 4** Considering and defining the circumstances of the installation – venue and weather conditions (summer is the best season for the installation)
- 5** Recruiting student groups to take part in the design – creating an open call, so any student can apply
- 6** Creating the conceptual brief
- 7** Brainstorming with students
- 8** Creating concept directions and submitting them to the partner or host event (event – if applicable) to select one path
- 9** Using artistic tools and software to create the plan and the structure
- 10** Purchasing the materials and creating a 1:1 structure (wooden frame) and the water pool
- 11** Creating the installation which is an artistic development process as well
- 12** Assigning demonstrators to operate the installation
- 13** Dismantling and assembling at other location (or storage)

21
PHOTOS

Photos: Antal Bodóczy

EVALUATION AND REFLECTION

22 LESSONS LEARNED

- ▶ Define and plan the afterlife / life cycle of an installation in advance
- ▶ Use degradable and recyclable materials for reusing purposes
- ▶ After-care is an important aspect to be taken into consideration during the planning process
- ▶ Documentation is essential and it can be used for promotion and help the life cycle of the installation

23 KNOWLEDGE GAIN

The installation is a conversation starter (the local water management company reached out for cooperation) this is also a sign that more art-based installation is needed to communicate messages to people. Analogue interaction is needed and a good tool to engage people.

24 PITFALLS / OBSTACLES

- ▶ Never underestimate the power of water (it has an effect on materials)
- ▶ Festival crowd can be difficult to handle
- ▶ Outdoor installations are dependent on the weather which is hard to predict

25 VARIATIONS (IF APPLICABLE)

It is possible to assemble the installation at different location with a variable framework.

26 TIPS FOR FUTURE IMPLEMENTERS / GOOD-TO-KNOWS

- ▶ Create a size and weight which is more compact for a travelling installation
- ▶ Take time as part of the installation and product development to make it easy to fold and focus on deplorability

27 RECOMMENDATION

- ▶ Covering also the human resources a tailor-made installation is costly, although it can greatly support an experience-based knowledge transfer.
- ▶ A more modular, or more compact installation set-up (think about the mobile coffee or newspaper station fixed on a cargo bike) can be also realized, which makes it easier to roadshow with it, so the investment can pay off.
- ▶ Try to map events with wide outreach which might be open to hosting a section on sustainability and scientific topics.
- ▶ Start collaboration with different sectors, event organisers (festivals, picnics, urban gatherings) out of your scope and sector to find a hosting event.
- ▶ Involve an installation or media artist or an architect, product designer who can help you frame and ideate.
- ▶ It is also possible to create an open call for artists to apply with a concept on "art installation to bring closer bioeconomy".

MOME SOCIAL IMPACT HACKATHON

ACTIVITY HOST / ORGANISER

MOME Innovation Centre is the main organiser, cooperating partners have been the British Council Hungary and Microsoft UK.

1 TYPE OF THE ACTIVITY

The social impact hackathon is a facilitation and co-hosting activity from the main organiser's side; providing mentoring to support the ideation and the design thinking process by mentors knowledgeable in design thinking, and providing subject matter advice from (industry) experts. Training (before the hackathon) was also an integral element in MOME's most recent hackathon; during the February event training on the basics of artificial intelligence and machine learning was delivered by Microsoft UK experts, and hackathon participants were able to deploy that learning in a practical way. Co-creation takes place in the interdisciplinary teams as they further develop their ideas, with the support of mentors, experts and tutors through the above processes.

2 FORMAT

It's an open, offline event involving higher education students with interdisciplinary backgrounds, who work together intensely for 24 hours to find workable, well-designed solutions to social and environmental challenges of the 21st century. Prior to this sprint-like competition, there was interactive training for 1.5 days.

3 THEME / CHALLENGES

MOME's Social Impact Hackathons are organised twice a year. The focus of these events changes from event to event. However, the goal is always to find workable, well-designed solutions to social and environmental challenges of the 21st century. Most recently, the theme was "Artificial Intelligence for the Common Good", with the two main challenge topics being related to climate change and food waste.

4 AIM OF THE ACTIVITY

MOME's Social Impact Hackathons aim to nurture young talent and find practical applications of design competences, address the grand challenges of the 21st century, and in the case of the most recent event, find practical use cases for artificial intelligence for the common good

5 SHORT DESCRIPTION

There is a great variety of hackathons out there. However, what makes MOME's Social Impact Hackathons special, is that they are design-driven, educational, interdisciplinary and international. As a part of the MOME Innovation Center and its Incubation Program's open innovation initiatives, the Social Impact Hackathons aim at nurturing young talent and finding practical application of design competences. It's a flagship event series, taking place twice a year. The sprint-like competitions engage interdisciplinary groups of talented people and facilitate the process to find workable, well-designed solutions to social and environmental challenges of the 21st century. This open innovation event encourages participants to test and expand their skill set in a fun yet competitive environment, while also encouraging young adults to network with others outside their regular classroom, university and field of study. Teams with innovative ideas also have the opportunity to get invited to participate in MOME's Incubation Program, where they get to further develop their ideas into more developed business concepts.

6 ORGANIZER TEAM

The organising team for MOME's Social Impact Hackathon has the following human resource needs:

- ▶ professional support from mentors, subject matter experts, jury members (and technical tutors, if needed)
- ▶ 5-6 people working behind the scenes on operations, logistics, marketing and communications.

7 TARGET GROUP

University students from diverse backgrounds, young innovators, recent graduates, young professionals, and any young adult interested in sustainability and entrepreneurship. There are also plans to open up these events to extend beyond young adults (i.e. without age limits).

8 CRITICAL NUMBER OF PARTICIPANTS

Minimum number: 30
Ideal number: 50
Maximum number: 60

9 DURATION

The hackathons usually last 24-48 hours. If a training element is included, then 1 or 1,5 days are dedicated to this before the hackathon.

10 PREPARATION PERIOD

The regular preparation time needed is approximately 2-3 months, which can be extended to 4-5 months if a co-creation process is put in place to co-design the hackathon challenge in a way that involves different stakeholders who can each provide a different perspective to the same challenge.

11 LOCATION

The activity takes place at the MOME campus. It is important to have a large space for the plenary sessions and for participants to be able to work comfortably in their teams. The provision of smaller meeting rooms can also be useful for teams to have short private meetings, and a "chill zone" has also proven to be helpful for teams to relax, unwind, and have some fun in-between the intense teamwork and ideation processes.

12 BUDGET AND SOURCES OF FINANCING

Approx. 10,500-13,000 EUR, which includes the prize for the winning team (which, this year, included the costs of a study trip to the UK). The budget was covered by sponsors; in exchange, they were provided with brand visibility, participation as jury members and mentors, and access to fresh ideas and young talent. There is also generally an intention to try to have two challenges sponsored by different donors.

13 SETTING AND MATERIALS NEEDED

Microphones, a projector, strong wifi, space for the teams to work in, desks, power cables and extension cords, flipchart paper, pens.

14 INFORMED CONSENT AND COPYRIGHT ISSUES (IF APPLICABLE)

No copyright issues, as ideas generated at the hackathon are the participants', MOME has no claim over them. Data collection complies with the university's GDPR rules.

15 OUTPUTS (IF APPLICABLE)

- ▶ Pitches delivered to the jury - in the most recent hackathon pitches were about AI web-based solutions to social and environmental challenges, relating to climate change or food waste.
 - ▶ Skills development - both as a result of the training and the co-creation process
 - ▶ Network building among fellow participants, organisers, and everyone providing professional support to the teams
 - ▶ Innovative ideas that can address burning issues
 - ▶ Awareness raising
- The most successful teams made it to MOME's Incubation Programme, some of them are related to the circular bioeconomy, food waste, and are focusing on the following, for example: Deploying AI for waste sorting; Installing a scale in garbage collection to measure food waste and raise awareness about it; Developing "vegan leather" alternatives from biodegradable material.

16 IMPACT

- ▶ Participants develop new skills
- ▶ Ideas are developed which may go into an incubation process
- ▶ Brand building (for MOME, partners and sponsors)
- ▶ Partnership building with mentors and experts - some of the mentors are now becoming mentors in the Incubation Program

17 TOOLS

Mentoring, coaching
Award for winning team (1000 EUR)
Technical tutoring
MS Teams was used for coordination, uploading content, accessing study material
Canvas - optional (AI setup in the case of the February hackathon)

18 COMMUNICATION

- ▶ Social media, including posts before, during, and after the event and paid ads
- ▶ Posters
- ▶ Neptun
- ▶ Newsletters to previous participants

19 METHOD

- ▶ The methods are mainly linked to prior training to maximise the participant's experience of the hackathon, as well as to enhance the overall quality of the pitched ideas.
- ▶ Hackathon challenges could also be shared in advance fo the event to enable participants to read up on the challenge area prior to the event.
- ▶ Having subject matter experts present also helps ensure that participants do not waste time on creating solutions that already exist or which are otherwise not practical/feasible.
- ▶ Design thinking and human-centered design methods are applied

20 STEP-BY-STEP INSTRUCTIONS

- 1 Reserve a date.
- 2 Specify the broad topic(s).
- 3 (Co-)design the hackathon challenge - a sponsor could bring in a challenge that matters to them, or you can co-design it with different stakeholders.
- 4 Recruit all professional support (mentors, experts, tutors, trainers).
- 5 Design the agenda of the whole event, make sure to allow for engagement periods and also free time for teams to work independently. Include icebreakers and networking occasions.
- 6 Develop a marketing and communications plan, and then actively promotion of the event.
- 7 Manage the whole application and registration process of participants.
- 8 Set up the venue.
- 9 Host the event and engage with the registered participants.
- 10 Post-event communications (social media, sharing photos, feedback forms, etc.).

EVALUATION AND REFLECTION

21 LINKS AND PHOTOS

IC BRITISH COUNCIL

Photos: Máté Lakos

[MOME WEBSITE](#)

22 LESSONS LEARNED

- ▶ There are many experienced mentors, experts, tutors and jury members who are motivated to provide professional support for free.
- ▶ Provide more time for team formation and networking.
- ▶ Artificial intelligence is not a popular theme/topic for art and design students at MOME.
- ▶ Constantly repeat the agenda and how each activity will work. There are many participants (and professionals supporting the event) who do not read previous communications, or who otherwise forget previous briefings.
- ▶ A consistent or standardised approach may be needed by the organisers and mentors to appropriately manage internal conflicts among the participating team members (i.e. deciding when to split up a team vs. forcing them, with good intent, to learn how to manage and overcome their internal differences).
- ▶ Unbundling the combination where the winning hackathon team automatically participates in the Incubation Program, as it may not necessarily be a good fit for the program and its established mentor network.

23 KNOWLEDGE GAIN

- ▶ Knowledge gain from the participants' perspective
 - ▷ Learning about the subject matter
 - ▷ Skills development (canvas, AI)
 - ▷ Network building
- ▶ Knowledge gain from the sponsors' perspective
 - ▷ New ideas
 - ▷ New talents
- ▶ Knowledge gain from the organiser's perspective
 - ▷ New ideas
 - ▷ New connections - with mentors, young innovators and sponsors
 - ▷ Experience

24 PITFALLS / OBSTACLES

- ▶ The generated ideas and concept do not meet the requirement of the sponsors
- ▶ Results can be superficial regarding social sustainability
- ▶ It is hard to make the market understand that concept draft is not a ready-made product and requires further development
- ▶ Follow up incubation is needed but long-term commitment from teams are hard to manage

25 VARIATIONS (IF APPLICABLE)

- ▶ Timeframe: If there is no training element included, then the hackathon/idea development phase lasts 48 hours.
- ▶ Challenges can be co-created together with stakeholders, instead of/in addition to using ones defined by sponsors
- ▶ The age limit (18 to 35 y.o.) may be lifted for the hackathons as there is an interest among older age groups as well.

26 TIPS FOR FUTURE IMPLEMENTERS / GOOD-TO-KNOWS

- ▶ Be content driven but do not expect the impossible innovation-wise
- ▶ Find a place which is cosy enough to spend 48 hours
- ▶ Carefully choose the working language to avoid exclusion
- ▶ Take care of the participants learning journey
- ▶ Carefully select the mentors, besides thematic knowledge pedagogical skills are expected

27 RECOMMENDATION

Exhibitions, fun quizzes, "chill zones", and having a music DJ for the networking session, all contribute towards creating a nice vibe.

MOOC CIRCULAR FASHION: Design, Science and Value in the Sustainable Clothing Industry

ACTIVITY HOST / ORGANISER

Wageningen University & Research (WUR) & ArtEZ University of the Arts

1 TYPE OF THE ACTIVITY

Massive Online Open Course (MOOC) = educational

2 FORMAT

Interactive online course

Photo: Wageningen University

3 THEME / CHALLENGES

Circular and Sustainable Fashion

4 AIM OF THE ACTIVITY

This online course aims to provide a comprehensive introduction to circular fashion for BA and MA students and practitioners in the field of textile and fashion design, production and retail.

5 SHORT DESCRIPTION

This online course is a comprehensive introduction to circular fashion, brought by roughly thirty different experts from both academia and practice. This course provides designers, retailers, scientists and all working in the industry or with an interest in fashion with holistic insights into the complex challenges of circular fashion, while engaging learners to start the transition to circularity within personal and/or professional practices. The course brings together art, design and science to move beyond an ego-centric approach to fashion and start from an ecosystem perspective. Learn the theory, understand the practice and stimulate learners to start their own circular fashion journey.

After this course, learners will be familiar with the core concepts and tools to help better understand circular economy in the context of the fashion industry. Some of the topics that are covered focus on understanding the challenge of recycling, design for circularity, alternative textiles through bio-based innovation and circular business modelling to help bring innovations to the market. After completion of this course, learners will be able to:

- ▶ Understand the role of sustainability and circularity in fashion
- ▶ Understand the importance of design for disassembly and recycling
- ▶ Evaluate new bio-based materials for textiles and understand the change in production processes
- ▶ Disrupt current thinking and mindset in the fashion industry and govern the transition to circular fashion
- ▶ Understand economic paradigms and new forms of value creation for circularity in the fashion industry

6 ORGANIZER TEAM

A core team of teachers and researchers for content development and a supporting team for online course development. In addition, a group of international partners for contributions like knowledge clips, doing interviews and moderating sessions, podcasts, etc.

7 TARGET GROUP

Higher education students (BA and MA level) from all over the world

8 CRITICAL NUMBER OF PARTICIPANTS

NA

9 DURATION

6 weeks, 16–24 hours per week

10 PREPARATION PERIOD

Complete content development and production cc. 8-10 month (1500 working hours)

11 LOCATION

Online (see MOOC Circular Fashion: Design, Science and Value in a Sustainable Clothing Industry - WUR)

12 BUDGET AND SOURCES OF FINANCING

Project costs ca. € 60.000,- - € 150.000,- (45/55% staff costs/material costs), external cash funding, internal co-funding by in-kind hours and production facilities

13 SETTING AND MATERIALS NEEDED

Studio facilities for recording (green screen) videos and podcasts

14 INFORMED CONSENT AND COPYRIGHT ISSUES (IF APPLICABLE)

Intellectual property rights for existing materials used for the course (images, videos, etc.)

20 STEP-BY-STEP INSTRUCTIONS

- 1 Determine topic and course outline
- 2 Find the right online platform for your course
- 3 Find internal and external funding and in cash and in-kind co-financing
- 4 Design the course in separate but related course modules
- 5 Determine for each module the content and the form of knowledge sharing (videos, podcasts, interviews, articles, texts, assignments, etc.)
- 6 Execute every part of the module
- 7 Run the course
- 8 Close the course and follow up with the participants

21 LINKS AND PHOTOS

Photos: Daniëlle Bruggeman, design-4-sustainability.com & Research

MOOC CIRCULAR FASHION:
DESIGN, SCIENCE AND VALUE IN A SUSTAINABLE
CLOTHING INDUSTRY - WUR.

15 OUTPUTS (IF APPLICABLE)

The videos and podcast as part of the course

16 IMPACT

Already 26.863 participants worldwide

17 TOOLS

Video editing and graphic design software and a website including chat / subscription functions

18 COMMUNICATION

Communication via WUR and the edX platform for online education

19 METHOD

The course consists of knowledge clips, assignments by closed questions, practical assignments, chat platforms.

EVALUATION AND REFLECTION

Consortium:

// Multi-stakeholder engagement to strengthen regional bioeconomy value-chains //

 www.engage4bio.eu

 info@engage4bio.eu

@Engage4BIO

